

A Multi-Leader Multi-Follower Stackelberg Game for Dynamic Spectrum Sharing in a Blockchain Enabled Cell-Free Massive MIMO Scenario

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ABSTRACT The stringent quality-of-service (QoS) requirements that are being considered for the sixth generation (6G) of mobile networks will necessarily imply the synergistic application of different mechanisms ranging from physical layer processing to radio resource management aspects. In particular, this work blends three complementary techniques that are bound to play a central role in the transition towards 6G. Firstly, cell-free massive MIMO (CF-mMIMO) is often heralded as a foundational physical layer technique that is able to address the demanding spectral efficiencies (SEs) planned for 6G. Secondly, dynamic spectrum sharing (DSS) has shown its potential to optimize the exploitation of the always-scarce radio spectrum. Finally, blockchain technology is used to make these bandwidth transactions fair and accountable. This work presents a general architecture where multiple sellers and buyers of spectrum can dynamically trade spectral resources, leveraging CF-mMIMO-based wireless networks and guided by Stackelberg game theory. Notably, all parameters, operations, and outcomes of this trade protocol are securely recorded on a blockchain using smart contracts (SCs). Exhaustive numerical results are provided that showcase the effects different network parameters have on the network performance while also revealing the cost associated with blockchain processing when relying on several popular blockchain platforms.

INDEX TERMS Cell-free massive MIMO, dynamic spectrum sharing, Stackelberg game, blockchain, decentralized autonomous organization.

I. INTRODUCTION

A. CONTEXT

TARGETING the forthcoming wave of new applications and services such as extended reality, autonomous driving, ultrahigh definition video transmission or sub-cm positioning, to name a few, researchers at academic, industrial and standardization entities are currently investigating the foundations of the forthcoming sixth generation (6G) of mobile networks [1], [2]. While many unknowns remain, some specific technologies are bound to have an impact in 6G. Among others, new forms of massive multiple-input

multiple-output (mMIMO), novel approaches to spectrum exploitation, and a heavy use of blockchain technology have all been predicted to play a key role in the 6G ecosystem [1], [2], [3], [4].

Despite the incorporation of new frequency bands, the phenomenal surge in traffic demands presents significant challenges in terms of spectral efficiency (SE), which cannot be addressed solely from a physical layer perspective through the use of new mMIMO techniques, but rather require the integration of advanced resource management strategies that judiciously utilize the available spectrum [3]. One such

approach is dynamic spectrum management (DSM), cited in [1] as one of the enabling technologies towards 6G. When relying on DSM, operators are allowed to share and commercialize any portion of assigned spectrum that is temporally underutilized so that this can be exploited by other spectrum-starving operators. Critically, all these spectrum management-related transactions among operators must be accountable, decentralized, and fair. All these requirements can be fulfilled by relying on blockchain technology, yet another of the pillars that will surely play a role in 6G [4]. This work proposes a complete framework to implement a DSM strategy in a blockchain-enabled mMIMO 6G context whose operative is guaranteed to be accountable, fair and privacy-preserving. Over the following paragraphs, each of the constituting technologies are reviewed.

Cell-free networks: Over the last decade, mMIMO, rooted in the seminal work of Marzetta [5], has become a cornerstone of fifth generation (5G) networks [6]. By deploying a massive number of antennas at the base station (BS), it achieves SEs unattainable in earlier generations. More recently, cell-free massive MIMO (CF-mMIMO) has emerged as a key enabler for future 6G networks [2]. A CF-mMIMO network comprises many access points (APs) randomly distributed across the coverage area and connected to a central processing unit (CPU) that handles most baseband processing [7]. Unlike traditional mMIMO, which concentrates antennas at the BS, CF-mMIMO disperses them throughout the service area, placing infrastructure closer to users. This architecture improves macroscopic diversity and, via cooperative processing, mitigates cell-edge effects typical of cellular networks.

CF-mMIMO retains all key mMIMO features [7], [8]: channel hardening reduces fading impact, and favorable propagation enables simple linear precoding to achieve near-optimal performance [9]. It is now regarded as more spectrally efficient than co-located mMIMO [8]. Recent research has addressed precoder and combiner design, channel estimation, and power control (see [8], [10] for reviews). Another notable advantage of cell-free networks is their superior energy efficiency compared to co-located systems, thanks to flexible infrastructure activation and minimal cooling needs at the APs [11], [12], [13]. Ongoing studies are also investigating practical pathways for transitioning from cellular to CF-mMIMO architectures [12].

Multi-operator spectrum management: When multiple CF-mMIMO networks coexist in a shared coverage area, each operated by a distinct network operator (NO), spectrum management becomes essential for efficient radio resource allocation, especially across diverse frequency bands envisioned in 6G ecosystems [14]. Traditionally, networks serve users using spectrum statically allocated by regulators, ensuring non-overlapping bandwidths. However, such fixed allocation may lead to inefficiencies, with some networks having surplus spectrum and others experiencing shortages.

Dynamic spectrum management allows operators or regulators to allocate bandwidth more flexibly based on user

demands. This approach aligns with cognitive radio principles, where secondary operators utilize underused spectrum from primary operators [15], [16].

Beyond spectrum efficiency, the emergence of fourth generation (4G)/5G introduced models like mobile virtual network operators (MVNOs) to optimize resource usage [17], [18]. An MVNO delivers telecom services without owning infrastructure or spectrum, instead purchasing capacity from mobile network operators (MNOs) or spectrum providers (SPs), where SPs may represent central authorities or other M(V)NOs engaged in bandwidth trading.

This work explores scenarios in which MVNOs own infrastructure but lack spectrum, requiring them to buy it. Implementing dynamic spectrum sharing (DSS) in such contexts improves utilization by dynamically allocating bandwidth to virtual operators willing to purchase it [19], outperforming static assignments [20]. Allocation occurs periodically or in response to significant network changes [21], often via optimization methods. Game theory is a proven tool to manage competition among NOs/SPs, optimizing spectrum use based on utility functions [22], [23], [24]. Depending on the assumptions, different game structures apply. A key distinction is whether players cooperate and share information (cooperative games), or pursue conflicting goals with limited knowledge of others' actions (non-cooperative games).

Non-cooperative strategies suit environments like ours, where distributed solutions are needed without centralized control and each player maximizes its own benefit. Within non-cooperative games, various designs exist. For instance, prospect theory-based approaches incorporate loss aversion and have been applied successfully in spectrum management [25]. When players lack full knowledge of others' actions, Bayesian games introduce probabilistic models to capture uncertainty [26]. In this work, we focus on Stackelberg games, a widely used framework for dynamic spectrum allocation in cognitive radio and multi-operator contexts [27], [28]. Stackelberg games feature leaders and followers; leaders know the followers' responses and optimize accordingly, forming a subclass of perfect information games. In our setup, SPs act as leaders, they own the spectrum and set the price. NOs act as followers, deciding how much bandwidth to purchase at that price. This asymmetry models the authority SPs have over NOs as resource owners. For a comprehensive overview of game theory and Stackelberg games in wireless optimization, see [26].

Blockchain technology and smart contracts (SCs): Managing spectrum resources across multiple SPs and NOs requires infrastructure and protocols to track agreements. Blockchain has emerged as a robust solution for such registration tasks [29]. It is a decentralized, tamper-resistant ledger where transaction blocks are sequentially added to form an immutable chain. Each transaction is authenticated by its initiator, preventing later denial [30]. Blockchain networks are typically public or private, with

further classifications into permissioned, permissionless, and consortium types [31].

Public blockchains allow open, permissionless participation, anyone can read, write, and join the consensus. Their high decentralization and node diversity enhance security. For example, Ethereum's 4,000+ nodes [32] highlight the robustness of public blockchains. This distributed structure increases resistance to Byzantine attacks.¹ In contrast, private blockchains, managed centrally and limited to approved nodes, improve privacy, efficiency, and scalability but are less resilient to Byzantine failures.

Within both public and private settings, permissioned networks restrict access to specific roles, offering controlled decentralization. Permissionless networks are fully open. Consortium blockchains, a type of permissioned network, involve multiple organizations, providing partial decentralization.

In summary, public and permissionless blockchains stress openness and decentralization, while private, permissioned, and consortium types focus on control, efficiency, and security. Public blockchains use transaction fees; private and consortium models share infrastructure and costs.

Originally designed for cryptocurrency, blockchain now supports broader use cases. SCs address these needs and are implemented on various platforms. They are code snippets stored on blockchain nodes, triggered by authorized users with input parameters. Ethereum introduced SCs via Solidity, running on the Turing-complete Ethereum virtual machine (EVM) [34]. Other public blockchains like Polygon and Binance Smart Chain (BSC) also support the EVM.

SCs often need off-chain data but cannot independently access external sources, run periodic tasks, or securely handle sensitive operations like randomness. These limits are addressed via oracles, external entities that link blockchains to outside data [35]. Oracles may be centralized (one trusted source, single point of failure) or decentralized (multiple validators ensuring accuracy and resilience) [36].

Decentralized Autonomous Organization: A decentralized autonomous organization (DAO) is an innovative organizational model that operates without central authority, enabling collective governance by its members [37], [38]. Unlike traditional hierarchies, decisions in DAOs are made through democratic voting, typically facilitated by blockchain. SCs automate and enforce these decisions transparently, eliminating intermediaries, lowering costs, and improving efficiency [39], [40].

Key advantages of DAOs include transparency and community-driven decision-making. Without centralized leadership, members can propose and vote on initiatives, promoting shared ownership and alignment around common goals. This structure ensures decisions reflect collective, not individual, interests. Additionally, all actions, proposals, and

votes are immutably recorded on the blockchain, enabling verification and fostering trust while minimizing corruption. Such transparency supports fair governance and facilitates integration with other decentralized applications in the blockchain ecosystem [41].

B. RELATED WORK

Several blockchain-based DSS frameworks have recently been proposed, many incorporating Stackelberg game theory. However, most prior works combining Stackelberg games and blockchain address settings different from ours. Specifically, [42], [43], [44] focus on unmanned aerial vehicles; [45], [46] on 5G slicing; and [47], [48] on Internet of Things and Internet of Vehicles applications, respectively. The scenario in [49] is somewhat related but relies on a consortium blockchain, which introduces inherent security risks. Some works [46], [49] explicitly note that a few regulators manage blockchain operations, and most adopt reputation-based miner selection—offering weaker security than public blockchains. In [49], a SC executes the DSS strategy, triggered by a primary node within the network. However, this centralization creates a potential single point of failure, undermining system resilience and reliability. Furthermore, the proposed DSS model requires each organization or operator to contribute infrastructure resources, increasing administrative overhead. Notably, none of these proposals evaluate the operational or maintenance costs of consortium blockchains.

Few works address scenarios involving multiple SPs. An exception is [50], where multiple secondary users compete to acquire spectrum from multiple primary users using evolutionary game theory. This was extended in [51] to allow secondary users to purchase bandwidth from secondary-specific spectrum brokers. However, these studies primarily focus on competitive dynamics, neglecting network-specific characteristics. Another exception is the work in [52], which treats the case of multiple SPs but just considering a single buyer. We refer the interested reader to [53] for a recent survey on blockchain-based dynamic spectrum sharing technologies.

In earlier work by the same authors [54], a Stackelberg game theory-based framework [26] was proposed to optimize spectrum utilization for multiple CF-mMIMO-based MVNOs with a single SP. However, the single-SP setup oversimplifies blockchain intervention at the cost of reducing the flexibility and generality achievable in multi-SP configurations.

C. CONTRIBUTIONS

Building on our previous effort in [54], this paper deals with scenarios in which multiple leaders (spectrum traders) and multiple followers (cell-free based MVNOs) are allowed to engage in bandwidth exchange transactions. In particular, the main contributions of this paper are:

- A multiple-seller multiple-buyer non-cooperative Stackelberg game model is proposed where spectrum

¹A Byzantine attack occurs when some nodes in a decentralized network act maliciously, undermining consensus and potentially causing issues like double-spending [33].

sellers seek to maximize the profits of bandwidth trade while NOs (spectrum buyers) aim at maximizing an SE-related utility function. Solving the Stackelberg game involves the SPs (i.e., leaders) setting prices for their available bandwidths by solving a convex optimization problem while subsequently letting the NOs (i.e., followers) determine the amount of bandwidth to be purchased at the set prices by again resorting to convex optimization. Importantly, the game model is build on top of a physical-layer abstraction characterizing a CF-mMIMO-based wireless architecture.

- The execution and management of the proposed Stackelberg game model is implemented through various SCs deployed on the blockchain. Moreover, they can be adapted to the terms and conditions negotiated and agreed upon by the sellers and buyers. These SCs control the functions to be executed, who can execute them, and when can they be executed within the Stackelberg game. In addition, an oracle is used to automate the execution of the game, eliminating the need to assign specific tasks to individual participants, streamlining the process and reducing administrative overhead. This approach ensures that spectrum allocation is automated, transparent and traceable, as all actions are recorded on the blockchain, making them verifiable and auditable.
- Extensive numerical results are presented to demonstrate the merits of the proposed mathematical framework and the existing trade-offs when implementing different blockchain-based solutions. More in detail, the impact several key parameters (e.g., number of NOs and/or SPs) have on the performance of the system when considering two specific market scenarios (non-differentiated oligopoly (NDO) and differentiated duopoly (DD)) is first assessed. Next, the implementation costs and performance metrics related to the game's management and execution are analyzed across four different blockchain networks.

D. PAPER ORGANIZATION

The rest of the paper is organized as follows. Section II presents the system model with a detailed description of all the actors involved in this DSS ecosystem. Section III introduces a cell-free network abstraction in the form of achievable rates that serves, along with the utility functions, to formulate the DSS Stackelberg game described in Section IV. The methodology to solve the Stackelberg game is presented in Section V. Section VI describes the Blockchain-related operations to record all the operative of the spectrum trade. The assessment of the Stackelberg game results in relation to the CF-mMIMO parameters are presented in Section VII while performance results regarding the use of blockchain for different commercial platforms are provided in Section VIII. The main outcomes of this work are recapped in Section IX.

II. SYSTEM MODEL

In distributed spectrum management, multiple SPs and MNOs, often with competing interests and no pre-existing trust relationships, must coordinate resource allocation and trading. In this context, blockchain offers a tamper-resistant ledger and programmable logic through smart contracts, enabling fair interaction and rule-based access control without the need for a trusted intermediary. This architecture not only improves transparency and auditability but also facilitates the automation and enforcement of agreements, delivering operational and strategic benefits while reducing reliance on centralized entities. Therefore, the proposed system model relies on SCs deployed via blockchain to provide efficient spectrum allocation management. These contracts, as key components of spectrum allocation, require prior deployment to grant NOs and SPs access to their functionalities. Deploying SCs for the proposed spectrum management approach can involve various actors and strategies. SPs, as primary stakeholders, can handle contract deployment directly. Alternatively, delegating this responsibility to specialized entities can streamline the process, ensuring both expertise and accountability. A DAO offers a decentralized governance model where stakeholders collectively oversee contract deployment and management, enabling transparent decision-making and automating certain operations [39], [40].

In this model, a DAO [55], [56] is considered the best choice for ensuring fair decision-making among all parties in managing spectrum sharing. It is assumed that the DAO oversees 6G network-related processes, including deploying SCs for spectrum-sharing agreements service level agreements (SLAs) between SPs and NOs. The DAO can operate either on or off the blockchain, though its design and implementation fall outside the scope of this work. For simplicity, it is assumed that SPs and NOs have agreed to establish and operate a DAO to collectively manage network functionalities.

As conceptually shown in Fig. 1, a DSS scenario is considered where S SPs, indexed by $s \in \mathcal{S} = \{1, \dots, S\}$, sell chunks of bandwidth to C virtual CF-mMIMO NOs, indexed by $c \in \mathcal{C} = \{1, \dots, C\}$. The bandwidth owned by the s th SP is denoted by B_s . The c th CF-mMIMO network is composed of M_c geographically scattered APs, with each AP provisioned with an N_c -antenna array. These APs cooperate to jointly serve K_c single-antenna mobile stations (MSs) using the same time-frequency resources. All APs in a given CF-mMIMO network are linked to a CPU (or multiple CPUs) through ideal fronthaul links. The performance provided by the c th CF-mMIMO network will be generically represented by an achievable SE η_c (measured in bit/s/Hz).

The chunks of bandwidth to be allocated to each of the virtual NOs and the prices they have to pay to each SP are determined through a competitive game aiming at optimizing predetermined utility-related functions. These utility functions are related, on the one hand, to the revenue that each SP will obtain from the sale of the bandwidth,

FIGURE 1. System model depicting the main entities and variables used in this work. Numbering labels represent the steps taken by the proposed scheme that will be detailed in Section VI.

and on the other hand, to the benefits that each of the operators can derive from the service they provide to the associated MSs when exploiting the newly acquired bandwidth.

The management of spectrum allocation agreements is facilitated by a SC known as the SLA deployed in the blockchain. This SLA registers the SPs and NOs eligible to participate in spectrum allocation processes (offers bandwidth or requests for spectrum), and manages the parameters that govern this process. Additionally, the SLA deploys an MLMF SC used by both SPs and NOs. The MLMF ensures proper bandwidth allocation by executing the DSS algorithm based on the Stackelberg leadership model. Specifically, each SP communicates the available bandwidth to the SC (B_1, B_2, \dots, B_S) while the NOs, in turn, communicate their achievable SE ($\eta_1, \eta_2, \dots, \eta_C$). Using these data, and taking into account the utility functions to be optimized, the MLMF implementing the DSS algorithm is executed to determine the optimal chunks of bandwidth to be assigned to the NOs and the prices they have to pay to each SP. This *commercial* interaction between SP s and CF-mMIMO NO c is characterized by the pair (b_{cs}, p_{cs}) , where b_{cs} is the chunk of bandwidth that the NO acquires from the SP, and p_{cs} is the price per unit of bandwidth charged by the SP to the NO (measured in monetary units per Hertz).

The SCs should dynamically allocate bandwidth, which can be done at scheduled times or when certain conditions agreed upon by participants are met. However, SCs cannot directly interact with external data and systems. Our system consists of NOs and SPs, so one of them should request the execution of each required function. To prevent a specific entity from handling certain functionalities that must be fulfilled by the SLA, an analysis is performed using an oracle to securely connect off-chain systems to on-chain SCs.

III. MODELING THE SE

The propagation channels between APs and MSs are defined by small- and large-scale fading parameters. The former are presumed static during the time-frequency *coherence block*, and the latter (i.e., spatial correlation matrices) remain static over many coherence blocks and they are assumed to be known at the APs and/or the CPU [57], [58], [59], [60]. The channel between MS k and the m th AP in the c th CF-mMIMO network is modeled as $\mathbf{h}_{cmk} \sim \mathcal{CN}(\mathbf{0}, \mathbf{R}_{cmk})$, where $\mathbf{R}_{cmk} \in \mathbb{C}^{N_c \times N_c}$ is the spatial correlation matrix, and $\beta_{cmk} = \text{tr}(\mathbf{R}_{cmk})/N_c$, captures pathloss, shadowing, and antenna gains. Channels between a MS and different APs are independent, so the collective channel $\mathbf{h}_{ck} = [\mathbf{h}_{c1k}^T \dots \mathbf{h}_{cM_c k}^T]^T$ is distributed as $\mathbf{h}_{ck} \sim \mathcal{CN}(\mathbf{0}, \mathbf{R}_{ck})$, where $\mathbf{R}_{ck} = \text{diag}(\mathbf{R}_{c1k}, \dots, \mathbf{R}_{cM_c k})$ is block-diagonal.

Each CF-mMIMO network relies on time division duplex (TDD), with frames of τ_{f_c} samples fitting the coherence block.² Every frame is divided into an uplink (UL) training phase (τ_{p_c} samples), an UL payload transmission phase (τ_{u_c} samples), and a downlink (DL) payload transmission phase (τ_{d_c} samples), ensuring $\tau_{f_c} = \tau_{p_c} + \tau_{u_c} + \tau_{d_c}$. During the UL training phase, τ_{p_c} orthogonal pilot sequences are allocated deterministically to MSs, allowing some MSs to share the same sequence whenever $K > \tau_{p_c}$. For MS k , let \mathcal{P}_{ck} denote the set of MSs sharing its pilot sequence. The minimum mean square error (MMSE) channel estimate for \mathbf{h}_{cmk} is

²As in co-located cellular massive MIMO networks, TDD relies on the assumption of perfect reciprocity between the uplink and downlink channels so that the uplink acquired channel is also a good estimate of the downlink channel. Models are available to incorporate deviations from perfect reciprocity, collectively known as hardware impairments [61], however, their consideration is beyond the scope of this work.

given by [8]

$$\hat{\mathbf{h}}_{cmk} = \sqrt{P_p \tau_{p_c}} \mathbf{R}_{cmk} \Psi_{cmk}^{-1} \mathbf{y}_{cmk}, \quad (1)$$

where P_p is the pilot-symbol transmit power, and \mathbf{y}_{cmk} is the projection of the matrix of signals received at the m th AP on the pilot sequence allocated to MS k , that is,

$$\mathbf{y}_{cmk} = \sqrt{P_p \tau_{p_c}} \mathbf{h}_{cmk} + \sqrt{P_p \tau_{p_c}} \sum_{k' \in \mathcal{P}_k \setminus k} \mathbf{h}_{cmk'} + \mathbf{n}_{cmk}, \quad (2)$$

with $\mathbf{n}_{cmk} \sim \mathcal{CN}(\mathbf{0}, \sigma_u^2 \mathbf{I}_{N_c})$, and

$$\Psi_{cmk} = \mathbb{E} \left\{ \mathbf{y}_{cmk} \mathbf{y}_{cmk}^H \right\} = P_p \tau_{p_c} \sum_{k' \in \mathcal{P}_k} \mathbf{R}_{cmk'} + \sigma_u^2 \mathbf{I}_{N_c}. \quad (3)$$

The channel estimation error $\tilde{\mathbf{h}}_{cmk} = \mathbf{h}_{cmk} - \hat{\mathbf{h}}_{cmk}$ is independent of the estimate and follows the distribution $\tilde{\mathbf{h}}_{cmk} \sim \mathcal{CN}(\mathbf{0}, \mathbf{C}_{cmk})$, where

$$\mathbf{C}_{cmk} = \mathbf{R}_{cmk} - P_p \tau_{p_c} \mathbf{R}_{cmk} \Psi_{cmk}^{-1} \mathbf{R}_{cmk}. \quad (4)$$

To allocate bandwidth and set prices for NOs, this work employs a Stackelberg game based on the SEs offered to MSs. Focusing on UL SEs without loss of generality, the centralized UL operation is assumed, where all baseband processing occurs at the CPU. The achievable UL SE for MS k in the c th CF-mMIMO network (in bit/s/Hz) is [8, Section V.1]

$$\eta_{ck} = \frac{\tau_{uc}}{\tau_{fc}} \mathbb{E} \left\{ \log_2(1 + \text{SINR}_{ck}) \right\}, \quad (5)$$

where the pre-log factor τ_{uc}/τ_{fc} reflects the fraction of the coherence block used for UL transmission. The instantaneous effective signal-to-interference-plus-noise ratio (SINR) is given by (6), as shown at the bottom of the next page, with the expectation taken over the aggregate channel estimates $\hat{\mathbf{h}}_{ck} = [\hat{\mathbf{h}}_{c1k}^T \dots \hat{\mathbf{h}}_{cM_k k}^T]^T$. Various combining filters, such as maximal ratio combining (MRC), MMSE, or zero-forcing (ZF), can be used, each leading to different SINRs and SEs. It should be stressed that all the signal processing steps described in this section, most notably, channel estimation, combiner design and power allocation, can all be implemented in a scalable manner. Scalability in a cell-free context refers to the fact that the complexity of all operations remain computationally bounded even when the number of users goes to infinity [8].

IV. FORMULATION OF THE STACKELBERG GAME

Let us denote by \mathbf{B} the $C \times S$ matrix containing the chunks of bandwidth acquired by the CF-mMIMO NOs from the SPs, and by \mathbf{P} the $C \times S$ matrix containing the prices per unit of bandwidth paid by the NOs to the SPs. Let us also denote by $\mathbf{b}_c^{(CF)} = [b_{c1} \dots b_{cS}]^T$ the vector containing the chunks of bandwidth acquired by the CF-mMIMO NO c from the S SPs, and by $\mathbf{b}_s^{(SP)} = [b_{1s} \dots b_{Cs}]^T$ the vector containing the chunks of bandwidth sold by the s th SP to the C NOs. Analogously, let us denote by $\mathbf{p}_c^{(CF)} = [p_{c1} \dots p_{cS}]^T$ the vector containing the prices per unit of bandwidth paid

by the CF-mMIMO NO c to the S SPs, and by $\mathbf{p}_s^{(SP)} = [p_{1s} \dots p_{Cs}]^T$ the vector containing the prices per unit of bandwidth charged by the s th SP to the C NOs. The objective of each of the S SPs is to maximize its own revenue obtained from selling the bandwidth to the NOs. Mathematically, the revenue of the s th SP can be formulated as

$$R_s(\mathbf{b}_s^{(SP)}, \mathbf{p}_s^{(SP)}) = \sum_{c=1}^C b_{cs} p_{cs}. \quad (7)$$

Note that under the Stackelberg game formulation, the bandwidths $\mathbf{b}_c^{(CF)}$ acquired by the c th NO are actually a function of the prices $\mathbf{p}_c^{(CF)}$. That is, the chunks of bandwidth that a particular CF-mMIMO NO is willing to purchase to the SPs depend on the prices charged by these providers. As the bandwidths available at the SPs are limited, the SPs must determine the prices that maximize the revenue under the aggregate bandwidth constraint. The constrained optimization problem at each of the SPs can then be formulated as

$$PSPs: \quad \max_{\mathbf{p}} R_s(\mathbf{b}_s^{(SP)}, \mathbf{p}_s^{(SP)}) \quad (8a)$$

$$\text{subject to} \quad \sum_{c=1}^C b_{cs} \leq B_s \quad (8b)$$

$$p_{cs} \geq 0 \quad \forall c \in \mathcal{C}. \quad (8c)$$

Inspired by the work of Singh and Vives [62], a suitable utility function for the c th NO can be defined as

$$U_c(\mathbf{b}_c^{(CF)}, \mathbf{p}_c^{(CF)}) = \eta_c \sum_{s=1}^S \alpha_{cs} b_{cs} - \sum_{s=1}^S p_{cs} b_{cs} - \frac{1}{2} \left(\sum_{s=1}^S \beta_{cs} b_{cs}^2 + 2\gamma_c \sum_{s \neq s'} b_{cs} b_{cs'} \right), \quad (9)$$

where α_{cs} (measured in currency units per bit/s) and β_{cs} (measured in currency units per squared Hz) are positive, and $\eta_c = \sum_{k=1}^{K_c} \eta_{ck}$ denotes the aggregate SE (measured in bit/s/Hz) of CF-mMIMO network c .

This utility function consists of three parts: the first term (positive) represents the revenue gained from exploiting the purchased spectrum; the second term (negative) corresponds to the payment for spectrum usage; and the third term (also negative) accounts for the cost associated with spectrum substitutability, where $-1 \leq \gamma_c \leq 1$ is the substitutability coefficient³ [62]. Analyzing the structure of the utility

³The substitutability coefficient γ_c quantifies the degree to which products offered by different suppliers act as substitutes or complements [62]. When $\gamma_c > 0$, the products are substitutes: purchasing a good from one supplier reduces the consumer's demand for similar goods from other suppliers. Conversely, when $\gamma_c < 0$, the goods are complements, meaning that the consumer derives greater utility from acquiring them jointly, increasing demand for multiple suppliers. In our context, spectrum is modeled as a homogeneous product (i.e., highly substitutable, with $\gamma_c > 0$) since the spectrum chunks offered by different SPs are assumed to be equivalent. That is, given a required bandwidth \mathbf{b}_{cs} , the NO c is indifferent as to which SP s provides the additional spectrum, as all are considered functionally interchangeable.

function reveals that, on the one hand, increasing the acquired bandwidth enables a CF-mMIMO NO to improve both spectral efficiency (SE) and profit. On the other hand, acquiring more bandwidth also raises the associated cost. In [63], Niyato et al. observed, within a context similar to the one considered here, that this utility function is concave and effectively captures the saturation of user satisfaction as the achievable SE increases. Furthermore, the first derivative of this quadratic function yields a linear bandwidth demand, which makes the resulting optimization problems analytically tractable. Analyzing the structure of the utility function, it becomes evident that, on the one hand, by increasing the acquired bandwidth, a particular CF-mMIMO NO improves both SE and profit. On the other hand, acquiring more bandwidth increases the cost. Therefore, bandwidth acquisition strategies are needed at the NOs to maximize their own utilities. In fact, the problem that must be solved by the CF-mMIMO NOs (followers' side) can be formulated as

$$PCFc: \max_{\mathbf{b}_c^{(CF)}} U_c(\mathbf{b}_c^{(CF)}, \mathbf{p}_c^{(CF)}) \quad (10a)$$

$$\text{subject to } b_{cs} \geq 0 \quad \forall s \in \mathcal{S}. \quad (10b)$$

Problems **PSPs**, for all $s \in \mathcal{S}$, and **PCFc**, for all $c \in \mathcal{C}$, form a non-cooperative Stackelberg game aimed at identifying the Stackelberg equilibrium point $(\mathbf{B}^*, \mathbf{P}^*)$ where both the SPs and NOs lack incentives to deviate. That is, for any point (\mathbf{B}, \mathbf{P}) such that $\mathbf{B} \geq \mathbf{0}$ and $\mathbf{P} \geq \mathbf{0}$, the Stackelberg equilibrium point $(\mathbf{B}^*, \mathbf{P}^*)$ satisfies

$$R_s(\mathbf{b}_s^{(SP)*}, \mathbf{p}_s^{(SP)*}) \geq R_s(\mathbf{b}_s^{(SP)*}, \mathbf{p}_s^{(SP)}) \quad \forall s \in \mathcal{S}, \quad (11a)$$

$$U_c(\mathbf{b}_c^{(CF)*}, \mathbf{p}_c^{(CF)*}) \geq U_c(\mathbf{b}_c^{(CF)}, \mathbf{p}_c^{(CF)*}) \quad \forall c \in \mathcal{C}. \quad (11b)$$

V. SOLVING THE STACKELBERG GAME

A. SUBGAMES OF THE CF-MMIMO NO

The first and second derivatives of $U_c(\mathbf{b}_c^{(CF)}, \mathbf{p}_c^{(CF)})$ with respect to b_{cs} are

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{\partial U_c(\mathbf{b}_c^{(CF)}, \mathbf{p}_c^{(CF)})}{\partial b_{cs}} \\ &= \eta_c \alpha_{cs} - p_{cs} - \beta_{cs} b_{cs} - \gamma_c \sum_{s' \neq s} b_{cs'}, \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

and

$$\frac{\partial^2 U_c(\mathbf{b}_c^{(CF)}, \mathbf{p}_c^{(CF)})}{\partial^2 b_{cs}} = -\beta_{cs}, \quad (13)$$

respectively. Since the second derivative is negative, the utility function is concave with respect to b_{cs} and, hence,

as the constraint is affine, each of the followers' games, mathematically modeled in (10), is a convex optimization problem and Karush-Kuhn-Tucker (KKT) conditions apply.

Lemma 1: Given a price vector $\mathbf{p}_c^{(CF)} = [p_{c1} \dots p_{cs}]^T$, the optimal solution for the chunks of bandwidth that must be acquired by the c th CF-mMIMO NO is

$$b_{cs}^* = \left(\zeta_{cs} - \varpi_{cs} p_{cs} + \kappa_{cs} (\mathbf{p}_{c-s}^{(CF)}) \right)^+ \quad \forall s \in \mathcal{S}, \quad (14)$$

with $x^+ = \max(0, x)$, $\mathbf{p}_{c-s}^{(CF)} = \mathbf{p}_c^{(CF)} \setminus \{p_{cs}\}$, and

$$\begin{aligned} \zeta_{cs} &= \frac{\eta_c \alpha_{cs}}{\beta_{cs} - \gamma_c} \\ &\quad - \frac{\gamma_c \eta_c \sum_{s'=1}^S \frac{\alpha_{cs'}}{\beta_{cs'} - \gamma_c}}{(\beta_{cs} - \gamma_c) \left(1 + \gamma_c \sum_{s'=1}^S \frac{1}{\beta_{cs'} - \gamma_c} \right)}, \end{aligned} \quad (15a)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \varpi_{cs} &= \frac{1}{\beta_{cs} - \gamma_c} \\ &\quad - \frac{\gamma_c}{(\beta_{cs} - \gamma_c)^2 \left(1 + \gamma_c \sum_{s'=1}^S \frac{1}{\beta_{cs'} - \gamma_c} \right)}, \end{aligned} \quad (15b)$$

$$\kappa_{cs} (\mathbf{p}_{c-s}^{(CF)}) = \frac{\gamma_c \sum_{s' \neq s} \frac{p_{cs'}}{\beta_{cs'} - \gamma_c}}{(\beta_{cs} - \gamma_c) \left(1 + \gamma_c \sum_{s'=1}^S \frac{1}{\beta_{cs'} - \gamma_c} \right)}, \quad (15c)$$

where the parameters of the system must be set in order to guarantee that ζ_{cs} , ϖ_{cs} , and $\kappa_{cs}(\mathbf{p}_{c-s}^{(CF)})$ are positive.

Proof: See Appendix. A ■

Thus, it can be observed that if the price is too high, that is, if $p_{cs} \geq (\zeta_{cs} + \kappa_{cs}(\mathbf{p}_{c-s}^{(CF)}))/\varpi_{cs}$, the c th CF-mMIMO NO will not buy any portion of the bandwidth available at the SP s and will be removed from this particular game.

B. SUBGAMES OF THE SPs

Using the optimal buying strategy of the NOs, mathematically expressed in (14), the optimization problem at the s th SP can be reformulated as

$$PSPR: \max_{\mathbf{p}_s^{(SP)}} \sum_{c=1}^C p_{cs} \left(\zeta_{cs} - \varpi_{cs} p_{cs} + \kappa_{cs} (\mathbf{p}_{c-s}^{(CF)}) \right) \quad (16)$$

$$\text{s. t. } \sum_{c=1}^C \left(\zeta_{cs} - \varpi_{cs} p_{cs} + \kappa_{cs} (\mathbf{p}_{c-s}^{(CF)}) \right) \leq B_s \quad (16a)$$

$$0 \leq p_{cs} \leq \left(\zeta_{cs} + \kappa_{cs} (\mathbf{p}_{c-s}^{(CF)}) \right) / \varpi_{cs}. \quad (16b)$$

This is a convex optimization problem (note that both the objective function and the constraints are linear functions of p_{cs}) and, again, the KKT conditions apply.

$$\text{SINR}_{ck} = \frac{\pi_{ck} \left| \mathbf{v}_{ck}^H \hat{\mathbf{h}}_{ck} \right|^2}{\sum_{\substack{k'=1 \\ k' \neq k}}^{K_c} \pi_{ck'} \left| \mathbf{v}_{ck'}^H \hat{\mathbf{h}}_{ck'} \right|^2 + \mathbf{v}_{ck}^H \left(\sum_{k'=1}^{K_c} \mathbf{C}_{ck'} \right) \mathbf{v}_{ck} + \sigma_u^2 \|\mathbf{v}_{ck}\|^2} \quad (6)$$

Lemma 2: Given the vectors of prices $\mathbf{p}_{s'}^{(SP)} = [p_{1s'} \dots p_{Cs'}]^T$, for all $s' \neq s$, let us define $\pi_s(\mathcal{C}) = \{c_{s1}, \dots, c_{sC}\}$ as a permutation of the set $\mathcal{C} = \{1, \dots, C\}$, where the CF-mMIMO NOs are sorted in such a way that

$$\begin{aligned} & \left(\zeta_{c_{s1}s} + \kappa_{c_{s1}s} \left(\mathbf{p}_{c_{s1}-s}^{(CF)} \right) \right) / \varpi_{c_{s1}s} \geq \dots \\ & \geq \left(\zeta_{c_{sC}s} + \kappa_{c_{sC}s} \left(\mathbf{p}_{c_{sC}-s}^{(CF)} \right) \right) / \varpi_{c_{sC}s}. \end{aligned} \quad (17)$$

Given $\pi_s(\mathcal{C})$, let us define $\tau_s(\mathcal{C})$ as the number of elements in the set \mathcal{C} that match the following condition:

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{\zeta_{c_{s\tau}s} + \kappa_{c_{s\tau}s} \left(\mathbf{p}_{c_{s\tau}-s}^{(CF)} \right)}{2\varpi_{c_{s\tau}s}} \\ & \geq \frac{\sum_{c' \in \pi_s(\mathcal{C}), c' < c} \left(\zeta_{c's} + \kappa_{c's} \left(\mathbf{p}_{c'-s}^{(CF)} \right) - 2B_s \right)}{\sum_{c' \in \pi_s(\mathcal{C}), c' < c} \varpi_{c's}}. \end{aligned} \quad (18)$$

Using this definition, the optimal solution for the prices per unit of bandwidth that must be charged by the s th SP to the C NOs is

$$\begin{aligned} p_{Cs}^* &= F \left(\mathbf{p}_{c-s}^{(CF)} \right) \\ &= \begin{cases} \frac{\zeta_{cs} + \kappa_{cs} \left(\mathbf{p}_{c-s}^{(CF)} \right)}{2\varpi_{cs}} + \frac{\lambda_s}{2} & \forall c \in \{c_{s1}, \dots, c_{s(\tau_s-1)}\} \\ \frac{\zeta_{cs} + \kappa_{cs} \left(\mathbf{p}_{c-s}^{(CF)} \right)}{\varpi_{cs}} & \forall c \in \{c_{s\tau_s}, \dots, c_{sC}\}, \end{cases} \end{aligned} \quad (19)$$

where

$$\lambda_s = \frac{\sum_{\tau=1}^{\tau_s-1} \left(\zeta_{c_{s\tau}s} + \kappa_{c_{s\tau}s} \left(\mathbf{p}_{c_{s\tau}-s}^{(CF)} \right) \right) - 2B_s}{\sum_{\tau=1}^{\tau_s-1} \varpi_{c_{s\tau}s}}, \quad (20)$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} & \left(\zeta_{c_{s(\tau_s-1)}s} + \kappa_{c_{s(\tau_s-1)}s} \left(\mathbf{p}_{c_{s(\tau_s-1)}-s}^{(CF)} \right) \right) / \varpi_{c_{s(\tau_s-1)}s} \\ & \geq \lambda_s \geq \left(\zeta_{c_{s\tau_s}s} + \kappa_{c_{s\tau_s}s} \left(\mathbf{p}_{c_{s\tau_s}-s}^{(CF)} \right) \right) / \varpi_{c_{s\tau_s}s}. \end{aligned} \quad (21)$$

Proof: See Appendix. B ■

Lemma 3: An iterative mechanism to update the vector of prices $\mathbf{p}_c^{(CF)}$ given the current prices $\mathbf{p}_{c-s}^{(CF)}$ proposed by other SPs in the network, can be obtained from (19) as

$$p_{cs}(t) = F \left(\mathbf{p}_{c-s}^{(CF)}(t-1) \right) \quad \forall c \in \mathcal{C}, \quad (22)$$

where t is the iteration index. This iterative update converges to a unique fixed point.

Note that the convergence of (22) does not depend on the number of users each NO is serving and, indeed, even when $K \rightarrow \infty$, each CF can be made scalable as stated in Section III, and the solution to (22) is guaranteed to converge.

Proof: See Appendix C ■

VI. BLOCKCHAIN-BASED SYSTEM DESIGN AND IMPLEMENTATION

Having posed the multi-leader multi-follower (MLMF) problem and proved how it can be solved optimally, it is now mandatory to describe how the information being input

into the game and the one resulting from its solution is kept in an auditable manner.

In the proposed system model, the SLA manages the deployment of the MLMF SC (referred to as MLMF) on the blockchain, which executes the DSS algorithm. Per SLA-defined rules, both SPs and NOs are notified when to submit their parameters to participate in each game round. Each SP publishes its available bandwidth for a given game execution, uniquely identified by an identifier (id), within the MLMF. NOs request participation by submitting their parameters. Once all data is received, the MLMF notifies the NOs that the game (identified by id) is ready to start and proceeds to solve it.

The SLA must also provide SPs and NOs with the address of the deployed MLMF, enabling updates to be disseminated to all participants. To facilitate communication, the MLMF uses events⁴—a blockchain mechanism for real-time updates and coordination throughout the Stackelberg game. Events are triggered at each DSS stage; for instance, when a SP declares bandwidth or a CF-mMIMO NO submits its parameters. This structured use of events ensures all participants remain informed throughout the process.

Interaction between SPs and NOs must meet security standards to ensure trust and reliability in bandwidth allocation. Consequently, all Stackelberg game processes must be transparent and auditable by both parties.

This work explores two approaches for resolving the Stackelberg game: 1) the game is solved off-chain (by an oracle or participant), and the SLA publishes results to the MLMF; or 2) the MLMF autonomously solves the game on-chain. In both cases, results must be published on the MLMF, communicated to all participants, and remain auditable by any entity, including third parties not directly engaged in the game. It is assumed that neither SPs nor NOs are required to set up, manage, or maintain a blockchain network.

A. STACKELBERG GAME SETUP

As explained, the proposed solution is divided into two SCs. The first contract, which is called MLMF, specifies the core logic for the provision of updated network parameters from SPs and NOs and the execution of Stackelberg games based on the received parameters. The second contract, which is called SLA, contains the terms and conditions to execute each step of the spectrum allocation protocol defined in the MLMF contract. Specifically, the SLA schedules the execution of the administration or management functions of the MLMF, which are required to be executed when the defined conditions are fulfilled to make the entire system work. Different solutions can facilitate the execution of these functions. While manual or off-chain alternatives may be viable in controlled environments, they present risks when participants have potentially conflicting interests or when strong guarantees of fairness and availability are required.

⁴An event is a feature in blockchain SCs used to notify external entities or participants of specific changes in the contract state [64].

FIGURE 2. Sequence diagram of Stackelberg Game Setup.

In such cases, decentralized oracle networks offer a more secure and impartial automation layer, reducing reliance on any single party and mitigating the risks of misbehavior or execution failure [65]. Therefore, a decentralized oracle is incorporated into the proposed solution, which leads the SLA to manage the interaction between the oracle and the MLMF.

The division of the proposed solution into the MLMF and SLA SCs allows the modification of the terms and conditions in the SLA without redeploying the core logic of the Stackelberg games held in the MLMF. Although in this paper the SLA is designed to handle only one MLMF for simplicity, the SLA could be configured to handle multiple MLMF contracts simultaneously to perform dynamic spectrum allocation. These contracts could differ in terms of setup parameters or use of allocation methods other than Stackelberg games. Even more, each contract could be dedicated to a specific subset of spectrum frequencies or to SPs and NOs with specific technical requirements.

As shown in Fig. 2, the deployment process of the two SCs begins with the deployment of the SLA by the DAO, which provides the configurable terms and conditions as initial parameters. Then, the SLA deploys the MLMF, which received the network parameters of α_{cs} , β_{cs} and ϵ , as well as, the blockchain addresses of each participant, both SPs (@SPs) and NOs (@NOs) in order to empower the MLMF to govern participant access, specifying which entities are authorized to engage in the games and execute specific functions of the MLMF. Although an initial list of both the SPs and the NOs will be provided, this list can be updated at any time thereafter. Once the MLMF is deployed, the SLA retrieves the MLMF's address (@MLMF) as it is needed to execute its functions.

Once the SLA and the MLMF are deployed, the DAO retrieves the SLA's address (@SLA) in order to indicate to the oracle the SC that should be executed. The DAO then registers the oracle's blockchain address (@oracle) in the SLA to ensure the oracle can perform the authorized functions of the SLA. Following the initialization process of both SLA and MLMF contracts, the execution of the Stackelberg game model can start.

B. STACKELBERG GAME EXECUTION

The primary objective of this section is to outline the operational logic of the MLMF SC specifically tailored to handle the operations described in the Stackelberg game, as

Algorithm 1 Solving the Stackelberg Game

Deployment:

\mathcal{C} , \mathcal{S} , and $\alpha_{cs}, \beta_{cs} \quad \forall c \in \mathcal{C}, \forall s \in \mathcal{S}$

SetupSP:

$B_s \quad \forall s \in \mathcal{S}$

Input:

$\gamma_c, p_c^{(CF)}, \eta_c \quad \forall c \in \mathcal{C}$

Run Stackelberg game:

Evaluate ζ_{cs} , ϖ_{cs} and $\kappa_{cs}(p_{c-s}^{(CF)}) \quad \forall c \in \mathcal{C}, \forall s \in \mathcal{S}$ modeled in (15a), (15b) and (15c), respectively

do

$p' = p$

Evaluate $\pi_s(\mathcal{C})$ and $\tau_s(\mathcal{C}) \quad \forall s \in \mathcal{S}$ (Lemma 2)

satisfying (17) and (18), respectively

Evaluate $\lambda_s \quad \forall s \in \mathcal{S}$ modeled in (20)

Evaluate p_{cs} and $\kappa_{cs}(p_{c-s}^{(CF)}) \quad \forall c \in \mathcal{C}, \forall s \in \mathcal{S}$ modeled in (19) and (15c), respectively

while $\sum_{c=1}^{\mathcal{C}} \sum_{s=1}^{\mathcal{S}} |p'_{cs} - p_{cs}|^2 \geq \epsilon$

$p^* = p, b_{cs}^*$ (modeled in (14)) $\forall c \in \mathcal{C}, \forall s \in \mathcal{S}$

Output:

Stackelberg point (b^*, p^*)

discussed in Section IV and specified in Algorithm 1, with ϵ denoting the required accuracy.

The multi-leader multi-follower Stackelberg game for our DSS protocol involves the following steps (see Fig. 3):

- 1) **Initialize a game round.** As explained in Section II, the SLA manages the conditions under which each game will run (agreed by the DAO). For example, it could be run at scheduled times or when certain conditions are met. This execution is controlled by the oracle, which periodically checks that the conditions in the SLA are met to start a new round of the game. When the conditions are met (*executeNeeded*, $t = t_{init}$), the oracle calls the SLA, which generates a unique identifier (*id*) associated with this round of the game, and instructs the MLMF to initiate the phase in which SPs provide their available bandwidth (*initialize(id)*). The MLMF emits an event (*initialized*) to inform SPs and NOs of the start of a new round.
- 2) **SPs Providing Bandwidth.** In this step, each SP publishes the available bandwidth for a specific game round (**SetupSP** function in Algorithm 1), identified by *id*, calling the *setBandwidth* function of the MLMF. The MLMF communicates the bandwidth published by each SP through an event (*EventBandwidth*), after verifying that the calling SP is authorized (i.e., that its blockchain address is included in the list of authorized addresses to participate in this game). Optionally, in the terms and conditions defined in the SLA, a maximum time limit for the SPs to provide their available bandwidth and participate in the game can be established.
- 3) **Starting Operator Parameters Provision.** Similar to Step (1), the oracle checks if the phase for NOs to provide their parameters should be initiated. If the

conditions are met, the oracle instructs the SLA to call the MLMF to update the status of the specific game round identified by id ($startInput(id)$). The MLMF emits an event to inform participants of the start of the parameters provision phase ($EventInputStart$). From now on, only SPs that have submitted their bandwidth in Step (2) can participate in the game.

- 4) **NOs Providing Parameters.** Each NO publishes the list of their parameters $(\eta_c, p_c^{(CF)}, \gamma_c)$ for a specific game round identified by id , calling the *input* function of the MLMF (**Input** function in Algorithm 1). The MLMF, in turn, communicates the parameters published by each NO through an event ($EventInput$), after checking whether the calling NO is found in the list of authorized addresses to participate in this game.
- 5) **Closing Operator Parameter Provision.** Similarly to Step (2), the terms and conditions defined in the SLA can establish a maximum time limit for the NOs to provide their network parameters and participate in the game. The oracle calls the SLA when the conditions defined in the SLA to terminate the parameters provision by NOs are fulfilled. Similarly to step (3), the SLA calls the MLMF to update the state of the specific game round identified by id , executing the *endInput* function. The MLMF, in turn, communicates the finalization of the phase through an event ($EventInputStop$). From now on, only NOs that have submitted their parameters can participate in the game.
- 6) **Run Stackelberg game.** Once all the parameters from both SPs and NOs have been published on the blockchain, the Stackelberg game is computed to get the spectrum allocation results. At this point, two different approaches are considered to solve the Stackelberg game:
 - a) *Off-chain approach.* The entity assigned according to the procedure defined in the SLA (i.e., the oracle or one of the participants of this game⁵) solves the Stackelberg game off-chain (**Run Stackelberg game** function in Algorithm 1) and submits to the SLA the results of the game (**Output** function in Algorithm 1), that is, the resulting optimal vectors, Stackelberg point $(\mathbf{b}_{cs}^*, \mathbf{p}_{cs}^*)$. The SLA checks whether this entity is authorized to publish this data and submits it to the MLMF, calling its *output* function. Then, the MLMF stores the results and emits an event to communicate the outcome to all participants of this game ($EventFinished$). Despite the fact that the results are computed off-chain by an entity, all participants possess knowledge of the algorithm, bandwidth and input parameters, enabling them to

validate the accuracy of the game-solving output by locally calculating the solution according to the Stackelberg formulation.

- b) *On-chain approach.* The assigned entity, following the procedure defined in the agreements, requests the SLA to solve the game identified by id . The SLA verifies that the requesting entity is authorized to execute the Stackelberg game and calls the MLMF, which runs the logic defined in the **Run Stackelberg game** function in Algorithm 1. This process results in the storage of the resulting Stackelberg point $(\mathbf{b}_{cs}^*, \mathbf{p}_{cs}^*)$. Once the results have been obtained, the MLMF records them on the blockchain and issues an event ($EventFinished$) to notify all involved entities (SPs and NOs). This implementation of the Stackelberg algorithm within the MLMF allows all participants to audit the game resolution process.

Every call to the functions of the MLMF and SLA are digitally signed by the entity originating the call and recorded on the blockchain. This not only ensures the integrity and authenticity of the provided data but also provides evidence of all the steps undertaken throughout the entire game process. That is, the information about who initiated the call to the SCs, when it was made, and the specific data provided are recorded and publicly available.

Note that steps (2) and (4) rely on the assumption that all participants commit to accept the result of the execution of the Stackelberg game. Therefore, once step (4) is completed, the contract is considered as signed, and the results published in steps (6)a and (6)b bind all the parties involved in steps (2) and (4). If any participant has provided incorrect data, the dishonest participant can be held responsible since the transactions of steps (2) and (4) have been signed by the corresponding SP or NO. Therefore, our system allows spectrum sharing in a dynamic way ensuring fairness throughout the process.

Therefore, the proposed system ensures security and resistance to attacks through multiple layers of protection. The immutability of smart contracts guarantees that once deployed, their rules cannot be altered, ensuring transparency and trust. The use of cryptographic signatures prevents unauthorized actions, while the authorization mechanism ensures that only legitimate participants can interact with the system. Additionally, blockchain's decentralization and consensus mechanisms make it highly resilient to manipulation and attacks, as compromising the network would require an unrealistic level of control over its infrastructure. These measures collectively ensure that the system remains tamper-proof, transparent, and fair for all participants.

VII. ASSESSMENT OF STACKELBERG EQUILIBRIA IN CF-MMIMO

This section starts by examining the interconnection between the Stackelberg game equilibrium and the number of SPs

⁵To select the entity responsible for executing the SC functions, various strategies can be employed. For example, the entity can be a SP or NO chosen randomly or it could be an external entity trusted by the participants. Regardless of the strategy chosen, it must be specified in the SLA contract.

FIGURE 3. Sequence diagram of MLMF Stackelberg game.

(leaders) and CF-mMIMO networks (followers), as well as the SE provided by the different CF-mMIMO NOs. This analysis delves into how these factors impact, on the one hand, the resulting prices the NOs must satisfy to the SPs and the chunks of bandwidth that these SPs allocate to the NOs; and, on the other hand, the utility perceived by the NOs and the revenue experienced by the SPs. Two particular scenarios will be considered in this analysis, namely, a non-differentiated oligopoly and a differentiated duopoly, whose characteristics are described as follows:

- *Non-differentiated oligopoly (NDO)*: This corresponds to a situation where there are an arbitrary number of SPs with $\alpha_{cs} = \alpha_c$ and $\beta_{cs} = \beta_c$ for all $s \in \mathcal{S}$, resulting in

$$\zeta_{cs} = \zeta_c = \frac{\eta_c \alpha_c}{\beta_c + \gamma_c (S - 1)}, \quad (23a)$$

$$\varpi_{cs} = \varpi_c = \frac{\beta_c + \gamma_c (S - 2)}{(\beta_c - \gamma_c)(\beta_c + \gamma_c (S - 1))}, \quad (23b)$$

$$\kappa_{cs}(\mathbf{p}_{c-s}^{(CF)}) = \frac{\gamma_c}{(\beta_c - \gamma_c)(\beta_c + \gamma_c (S - 1))} \sum_{s' \neq s} p_{cs'}. \quad (23c)$$

The parameters ζ_{cs} are always positive, and the positivity of ϖ_{cs} and $\kappa_{cs}(\mathbf{p}_{c-s}^{(CF)})$ can be guaranteed by setting $S \geq 2$ and $\beta_c > \gamma_c$.

- *Differentiated duopoly (DD)*: In the special case in which $S = 2$ we have a differentiated duopoly [62], for which

$$\zeta_{cs} = \frac{\alpha_{cs} \beta_{cs'} - \gamma_c \alpha_{cs'}}{\beta_{c1} \beta_{c2} - \gamma_c^2} \eta_c, \quad (24a)$$

$$\varpi_{cs} = \frac{\beta_{cs'}}{\beta_{c1} \beta_{c2} - \gamma_c^2}, \quad (24b)$$

$$\kappa_{cs}(\mathbf{p}_{c-s}^{(CF)}) = \frac{\gamma_c p_{cs'}}{\beta_{c1} \beta_{c2} - \gamma_c^2}, \quad (24c)$$

for $s, s' \in \{1, 2\}$, with $s' \neq s$. In order to guarantee the positivity of these parameters the conditions $\beta_{c1} \beta_{c2} - \gamma_c^2 > 0$ and $\alpha_{cs} \beta_{cs'} - \gamma_c \alpha_{cs'} > 0$, for $s' \neq s$, must hold.

A simulation setup is considered where the coverage area under analysis consists of a square of side $D = 1000$ meters over which the APs and MSs of the different CF-mMIMO networks are independently and randomly (uniformly) distributed. To mitigate boundary effects, wrap around is implemented [8]. A TDD frame of $\tau_{fc} = 200$ samples is considered, with the UL training phase allocated $\tau_{pc} = 20$ samples. It is assumed without loss of generality that UL and DL are allocated nearly equal number of samples for payload data transmission, leading to $\tau_{uc} = \lfloor (\tau_{fc} - \tau_{pc})/2 \rfloor$. The aggregate bandwidth available at the SPs is set to $B = 40$ MHz, and the power available at the MSs is set to $P_u = P_p = 100$ mW. The UL receiver noise is characterized

FIGURE 4. Impact of the number of CF-mMIMO NOs on the price per MHz (left), allocated bandwidth (middle left), operators' utility (middle right), and revenue of the SPs (right) experienced in a non-differentiated oligopoly scenario.

by $\sigma_u^2 = -94.93$ dBm. A centralized UL operation utilizing MMSE combiners is assumed (see [8, Corollary 5.3]), implementing the fractional power control strategy proposed by Demir et al. in [8, eq. (7.34)] with $\nu = -1/2$, thereby approximating max-min SE performance. The large-scale channel propagation gains between APs and MSs have been modelled as in [8, Section 2.5.2]. Moreover, assuming that the APs are equipped with half-wavelength-spaced uniform linear arrays (ULAs), the spatial correlation matrices \mathbf{R}_{cmk} have been computed using the local scattering model described in [8, Section 2.5.3] and setting both the azimuth and elevation angular standard deviations (ASDs) to $\sigma_\varphi = \sigma_\theta = 15^\circ$. All the numerical results shown next correspond to the outcomes of 10000 random layouts.⁶ with their corresponding Stackelberg solutions computed with accuracy $\epsilon = 10^{-2}$. According to [66], most areas with ultradense network deployments feature 3-4 physical MNOs with fixed-assigned spectrum (acting as SPs in this context) and approximately 10-20 MVNOs that lease bandwidth from the MNOs (acting as NOs in this context). The results presented below have been generated with these figures in mind.

A. IMPACT OF THE NUMBER OF NOs IN AN NDO

In order to gain a first insight into the operation of the Stackelberg game in an NDO scenario, results have been generated by considering that $S = 4$ SPs, with $\alpha_c = 5 \times 10^5$ currency units per bit/s, $\beta_c = 2$ currency units per square Hz and a substitutability coefficient $\gamma_c = 1$, serve different numbers of CF-mMIMO NOs under the assumption that all networks have the same parameters and serve the same number of MSs.⁷ The four SPs, denoted as SP 1, SP 2, SP 3 and SP 4, are assumed to share the total system bandwidth so that $B_1 = B/15$, $B_2 = 2B_1$, $B_3 = 4B_1$ and $B_4 = 8B_1$.

⁶A layout consists of a random spatial distribution of MSs and APs

⁷Note that the parameters describing the utility function have been selected to guarantee that the system is operating in the region of allocated bandwidths for which the prices are positive [62].

Moreover, a setup has been considered in which every CF-mMIMO network consists of $M_c = 80$ APs, each equipped with $N_c = 2$ antennas, and serving $K_c = 30$ MSs. Note that since all CF-mMIMO networks have the same parameters, their average SEs will be identical. As a result, an even split of the frequency resources is to be expected among the players. Fig. 4 presents the price per MHz (left), allocated bandwidth (middle left), operators' utility (middle right), and revenue of the SPs (right) when considering C NOs competing for the available bandwidth. In agreement with intuition, as the number of NOs participating in the game increases, each of them receives, on average, a proportionally smaller fraction of the available bandwidth. Moreover, the more NOs wishing to join the Stackelberg game, the greater the competition among them to access a scarce resource. Consequently, the higher the price per MHz each of them has to pay to obtain a lower amount of bandwidth assigned. This sequence of events logically results, on the one hand, in a decrease in the average utility experienced by each of the NOs and, on the other hand, in a clear increase in the average revenue experienced by the SPs at the equilibrium point of the Stackelberg game. Nonetheless, note how the price per MHz tends to saturate with an increasing number of competing CF-mMIMO networks, and consequently, the SP's revenue adheres to the law of diminishing returns.

In the aforementioned figures, it is also evident that SPs owning a larger amount of bandwidth are offering the unit of spectrum at lower prices than those SPs owning a smaller amount of bandwidth. However, owning a larger amount of bandwidth more than compensates for the decreased price per MHz, and consequently, the SPs that have a larger share of spectrum experience significantly higher average revenues than those with access to a limited portion of the spectrum.

B. IMPACT OF THE NUMBER OF SPs IN AN NDO

To gain further insight into the operation of the Stackelberg game in an NDO scenario, results are presented in this Subsection that have been generated by considering that

FIGURE 5. Impact of the number of SPs on the price per MHz (left), allocated bandwidth per SP (middle left), operators' utility (middle right), and revenue of the SPs (right) experienced in a non-differentiated oligopoly scenario.

a varying number of identical SPs, with $\alpha_c = 5 \times 10^5$ currency units per bit/s, $\beta_c = 2$ currency units per square Hz, a substitutability coefficient $\gamma_c = 1$ and with equal bandwidth split $B_c = B/S$, provide spectrum to $C = 4$ CF-mMIMO NOs, denoted as CF1, CF 2, CF 3 and CF 4, and experiencing dissimilar average SEs. In particular, a setup has been considered in which the CF-mMIMO networks consist of $M_1 = 70$ APs, $M_2 = 80$ APs, $M_3 = 90$ APs and $M_4 = 100$ APs, each equipped with $N_c = 2$ antennas, and serving $K_c = 30$ MSs provide achievable SEs $\eta_1 < \eta_2 < \eta_3 < \eta_4$ to their associated MSs.⁸

Again, Fig. 5 presents the price per MHz (left), allocated bandwidth (middle left), operators' utility (middle right), and revenue of the SPs (right). The first important result to note is that as the number of SPs in the system increases, and thus the available bandwidth they can trade decreases, the prices per MHz charged to CF-mMIMO NOs also increase. Furthermore, the larger the SE a CF-mMIMO NO can offer to their associated MSs, the higher the budget they have to satisfy the SPs, and the larger the chunks of bandwidth they are allocated. Due to these variations in prices per MHz and allocated bandwidth, the average utility perceived by NOs increases both with the SE they can provide to their associated users and with the number of SPs participating in the game. It is evident, however, that as the number of SPs increases, the average revenue perceived by each of them decreases. Importantly, since the coverage area remains fixed for all NOs, varying the number of APs is equivalent to fixing the number of APs while varying the network coverage area. In other words, the truly qualitative metric is the AP density per unit area (number of APs/m²). Also note that these different spectral efficiencies can be seen as different levels of user demands/requirements (in bits/s/Hz). A similar effect would be observed if the number of APs per NO was to remain fixed but the user load was varied on each cell-free network. This setup could serve to evaluate scenarios where different NOs have different numbers of subscribers.

⁸Qualitatively similar results are obtained by varying the number of antennas per AP or the number of MSs served by each CF-mMIMO NO.

C. IMPACT OF THE SUBSTITUTABILITY COEFFICIENT IN AN NDO

The scenario under consideration in this Subsection consists of $S = 4$ SPs, with $\alpha_c = 5 \times 10^5$ currency units per bit/s, $\beta_c = 2$ currency units per square Hz, and sharing the total system bandwidth B such that $B_4 = 2B_3, B_3 = 2B_2, B_2 = 2B_1, B_1 = B/15$, that provide service to $C = 4$ CF-mMIMO networks composed of $M_1 = 70$ APs, $M_2 = 80$ APs, $M_3 = 90$ APs, and $M_4 = 100$ APs, each equipped with $N_c = 2$ antennas, and serving $K_c = 30$ MSs. As shown in Fig. 6, where the price per MHz (left), allocated bandwidth (middle left), operators' utility (middle right), and revenue of the SPs (right) are presented as a function of γ_c , the substitutability coefficient has a significant impact on the Stackelberg game equilibrium. In particular, when the NOs can freely switch among the frequency spectra offered by the SPs (i.e., γ_c is high), the Stackelberg game equilibrium point results in smaller prices per MHz, regardless of both the SE that the CF-mMIMO NOs can offer to their associated MSs and the share of bandwidth available at each SP. In fact, since the NOs can easily switch to the cheaper spectrum, the degree of competition among the SPs increases, causing them to offer lower prices to attract NOs. As the price per MHz decreases, the average utility perceived by NOs increases, and the average revenue of the SPs experiences a significant decrease. Interestingly, the allocation of bandwidth to different CF-mMIMO NOs tends to be fairer as the substitutability coefficient increases. Even though NOs with higher SEs are allocated larger chunks of bandwidth, irrespective of the value of the substitutability coefficient, the larger the value of γ_c , the lower the variance of the amounts of bandwidth allocated to different NOs participating in the game.

D. IMPACT OF THE NUMBER OF NOs IN A DD

In this Subsection, a DD is considered where the two SPs, denoted as SP 1 and SP 2, and assumed to own the same amount of spectra (i.e., $B_1 = B_2 = B/2$), are characterized by a substitutability coefficient $\gamma_c = 1$, $\alpha_{c1} = 5.9 \times 10^5$

FIGURE 6. Impact of the substitutability coefficient on the price per MHz (left), allocated bandwidth per SP (middle left), operators' utility (middle right), and revenue of the SPs (right) experienced in a non-differentiated oligopoly scenario.

FIGURE 7. Impact of the number of CF-mMIMO NOs on the price per MHz (left), allocated bandwidth (middle left), operators' utility (middle right), and revenue of the SPs (right) experienced in a differentiated duopoly scenario.

FIGURE 8. Impact of the number of CF-mMIMO NOs on the CDF of the allocated bandwidth in a differentiated duopoly scenario.

currency units per bit/s, $\alpha_{c_2} = 6.1 \times 10^5$ currency units per bit/s, $\beta_{c_1} = 4$ currency units per square Hz, and $\beta_{c_2} = 2$ currency units per square Hz. These SPs provide spectrum to different numbers of CF-mMIMO NOs consisting of $M_c = 80$ APs, each equipped with $N_c = 2$ antennas, and serving

$K_c = 30$ MSs. As it can be observed in Fig. 7, where the price per MHz (left), allocated bandwidth (middle left), operators' utility (middle right), and revenue of the SPs (right) are presented as a function of C , the Stackelberg game outcomes are strongly influenced by the parameters α_{c_s} and β_{c_s} . In fact, as stated by Singh and Vives in [62], the proposed utility function gives rise to a linear demand structure and the inverse demands are given by $p_{c_s} = \alpha_{c_s} - \beta_{c_s} b_{c_s} - \gamma_c b_{c_s'}$, for $s, s' \in \{1, 2\}$, with $s' \neq s$. That is, the prices charged by a particular SP diminish with decreasing values of α_{c_s} and increasing values of β_{c_s} , and so does the corresponding revenue, as clearly observed in Fig. 7. Specifically, as $\alpha_{c_1} < \alpha_{c_2}$ and $\beta_{c_1} > \beta_{c_2}$, SP 1 offers lower prices per MHz to attract NOs, and consequently, it obtains a lower average revenue. As expected, with an increasing number of NOs in the game, the degree of competition among them increases. Consequently, the allocated share of bandwidth per NO decreases, and the price they must satisfy to the SPs rises. This leads to a reduced average utility and a significantly increased average revenue for the SPs. Interestingly, even though the two SPs allocate the

same average amount of bandwidth to each of the NOs participating in the game (see Fig. 7 middle-left), the CDF of the allocated bandwidth, presented in Fig. 8, clearly shows that the bandwidth allocation process at SP 1 is fairer than that at SP 2. Specifically, the NOs that are allocated a higher (lower) share of bandwidth by SP 1 are allocated an even higher (lower) share of bandwidth by SP 2.

VIII. BLOCKCHAIN PERFORMANCE ASSESSMENT

Our proposal can be deployed on any blockchain (public, private, or permissioned) based on the specific requirements of the scenario. For the feasibility analysis, we chose a blockchain that requires minimal trust while ensuring full transparency, and where participants don't need to deploy or maintain it themselves. Thus, we opted for public blockchains, which offer transparency in a trustless environment and are already operational, reducing the infrastructure and administrative burden for both SPs and operators.

Therefore, this section analyzes the effects of using public blockchains and the impact of the introduced oracle on the economic cost and delay of the main operations of the proposed solution. For this purpose, we assess the cost of using the MLMF SC in the scenarios considered in Section VII, to evaluate how the economic cost is influenced by the number of SPs and NOs, as well as the substitutability coefficient.

A. GAS COST OF THE STACKELBERG GAME FUNCTIONS

The complexity of executing each function within the contract is measured in gas units, a fixed measurement defined in [34]. As an illustration, the gas requirement for deploying a SC on the blockchain is fixed at 32,000 gas units, excluding the execution of any SC functions. Moreover, the cost measured in gas units remains constant across different EVM-based blockchains. As a result, the cost of executing MLMF functions, in terms of gas, does not vary irrespective of the EVM-based blockchain they are deployed on.

The MLMF SC was implemented in Solidity [64] and deployed on the Hardhat Network, a local Ethereum node for development. There are several utilities that facilitate the task to evaluate the costs, in gas units, of executing SCs. Here, we use the hardhat-gas-reporter plugin⁹ as it enables the straightforward creation of reports on gas consumption for each function.

The first step in running the Stackelberg game is the deployment of the contract on the blockchain. Considering the first, second, and fourth scenarios from Section VII, Fig. 9 shows the cost required to deploy the SC. The third scenario, which evaluates the impact of the substitutability coefficient, is not considered. This is because the cost of deployment depends on the size of the contract and the

FIGURE 9. Gas cost of the MLMF SC deployment: first, second and fourth scenario.

information included in its deployment. In this case, the number of NOs and SPs is fixed and the size of the variable storing the substitutability coefficient does not vary and thus, it has no effect on the deployment cost.

As shown in Fig. 9, the deployment cost increases with the number of SPs and NOs. The addition of more participants in the Stackelberg game increases the amount of data stored in the blockchain, which causes the growth of the cost. For example, this increase is approximately 166,000 gas units when adding an SP with $C = 4$ or when adding an operator with $S = 4$, while it increases approximately 118,000 gas units when there is an additional NO with $S = 2$. As we will see, the cost of deploying the MLMF is much higher than the cost of executing any of its functions. However, it doesn't impact on the Stackelberg game execution cost because the MLMF deployment is performed only once, while the game can be run as many times as needed over time without the need to redeploy the contract.

Once the SC is deployed, rounds of the Stackelberg game can be executed, following the steps defined in Section VI-B (see Fig. 3). Fig. 10 shows the gas cost of executing the MLMF main functions in the scenarios analysed in section VII and considering the off-chain approach (the game is solved off-chain and the results are published on-chain at a later stage). Similarly to the deployment, the variation in the substitutability coefficient does not affect the cost of the different functions (Fig. 10d).

With the exception of the *input* and *output* functions, the cost of the other MLMF functions is constant and independent of the number of game participants. This is because the amount of data stored in the blockchains is always the same. As observed, the highest cost is associated with publishing the results of the Stackelberg game (*output* function), which increases with the number of participants (both NOs and SPs). This is due to the high cost of data storage on the blockchain. Therefore, the more SPs and NOs there are, the more data that needs to be published related to the Stackelberg point. The cost of the *output* function increases approximately 182,000 gas units when adding an SP with $C = 4$ or adding an operator with $S = 4$, and approximately 91,000 gas units when adding an operator

⁹“Gas metrics for method calls and deployments on L1 and L2 blockchain networks”. Available: <https://www.npmjs.com/package/hardhat-gas-reporter>, accessed on 10 January 2025.

FIGURE 10. Gas cost of the MLMF main functions for the four considered scenarios.

with $S = 2$. The reason behind the same increment with $C = 4$ and $S = 4$ is the fact that \mathbf{B} and \mathbf{p} are matrices of dimensions $C \times S$, so with adding a new NO or SP an additional row or column respectively is stored.

The more providers offering bandwidth, the larger the requests made by NOs can be, and consequently, the higher the cost for the NOs (*input* function Fig. 10b). The cost of the *input* function increases approximately 22,600 gas units when there is an additional SP, but it doesn't change when modifying the number of NOs. This is because the *input* function stores an array of initial prices that has the same length as the number of SP and, hence, when adding an SP an additional value is stored in the blockchain.

The cost of the *solveStackelberg* function (on-chain approach where the game is solved by the MLMF) is presented separately (see Fig. 11) due to the significantly higher gas cost required for its execution compared to other functions. This high gas required is due to the substantial data storage on the blockchain and the numerous and complex operations performed by the SC. When analyzing the effect of the number of SPs, it is evident that this parameter has the most significant impact, as reflected in the initial case. This is primarily due to the increased information storage requirements, as seen in previous cases. Furthermore, when examining the Stackelberg resolution algorithm, it must be

executed until reaching an equilibrium point, as explained in Section IV. Therefore, a higher number of iterations results in more operations and, consequently, higher costs.

B. COST IN FIAT

The cost, expressed in units of gas, is a valuable fixed measure for identifying how changes in different parameters impact the solution and for comparing different solutions. Nevertheless, the economic cost of performing the various operations of the proposed solution also depends on the cryptocurrency price (which can have high volatility) and the gas price (which usually depends on the network conditions) associated with each blockchain network. To evaluate the economic cost of our solution, we chose Polygon, Arbitrum, Fantom, and BNB Chain because they are representative examples of modern blockchains, covering both Layer 1 and Layer 2 technologies. They use different types of consensus methods and offer different advantages, making them ideal for understanding the options available for building scalable and cost-effective blockchain solutions.

All these blockchains are EVM-compatible, meaning they support the Ethereum Virtual Machine and allow the deployment of SCs. Polygon and Arbitrum are Layer 2 solutions for Ethereum, designed to make Ethereum faster and cheaper through sidechains and rollups. BNB Chain and Fantom are Layer 1 blockchains, each with unique strengths.

FIGURE 11. Gas cost of the solveStackelberg function considering all scenarios.

BNB Chain is known for its speed, affordability, and strong connection to the Binance ecosystem, while Fantom uses a DAG-based system to enable fast and low-cost transactions. Even though Ethereum is the most popular public blockchain capable of executing SCs, it has been excluded due to its consistently high fees, as we have observed in other scenarios, and that renders it infeasible for the specific problem at hand [32], [54], [67].

As verified in Section VIII-A, the variation in the number of SPs affects the execution of the *input* function. The variation in both the number of NOs and SPs influences the cost of the *solveStackelberg* and *output* functions. However, these variations do not affect the cost of the rest of the functions, which remain constant. Based on this analysis, this section evaluates the cost in fiat currency over time for the previously described cases.

The average cost of the functions *initialize*, *setBandwidth*, *startInput* and *endInput* is shown in Fig. 12 for the scenario with $C = 4$ and $S = 4$. In this figure, the impact of cryptocurrency price volatility associated with each blockchain can be observed. There are noticeable peaks, often influenced by the demand for blockchain usage¹⁰ or news related to the blockchain’s utility. Table 1 provides an overview of the estimated costs (in US dollars) for the scenario with $C = 4$ and $S = 4$ (Fig. 12), based on the average, minimum, and maximum gas prices paid over a 12-month period (November 2023 to October 2024). As can be seen, the cost of the *initialize*, *setBandwidth*, *startInput*, and *endInput* functions is relatively low, with Polygon and Fantom being the two blockchains with the lowest prices. If an operator executes the *setBandwidth* function, the cost could reach a maximum of \$0.172 in Fantom (with an average value of \$0.008) and \$0.18 in Polygon (with an average value of \$0.011).

Analyzing Table 1, we can see that the most expensive functions, such as *solveStackelberg*, can reach prices of \$20 in Fantom and \$21 in Polygon. It is important to note that in this case, the game is solved on-chain, which adds load and cost. BNB Chain could reach maximum prices of \$141, significantly higher than the others. Although these maximums are occasional, they must be taken into account

¹⁰The high costs in Polygon from 16/11/2023 to 17/11/2023 were caused by the high demand for mining tokens inspired by Ordinals [68].

when analyzing which blockchain is the most appropriate for each specific scenario. The second most expensive function is *output* with maximum prices of \$1.34 and \$1.41 using Fantom and Polygon, respectively.

This analysis indicates that Polygon and Fantom offer more favorable average prices and lower standard deviations compared to the other evaluated blockchain platforms. To further examine the functions whose price fluctuates based on the considered scenario, we will present the price graphs using Polygon, as it is a widely adopted Layer 2 blockchain with a higher number of deployed SCs compared to Fantom.

1) IMPACT OF THE NUMBER OF SPs

To assess the influence of the number of SPs on the cost in fiat of running the functions *input*, *output*, and *solveStackelberg*, we fix $C = 4$ and vary the number of SP (from 2 to 8). Table 2a illustrates the cost associated with the three functions. The *input* and *output* functions, which are executed by an operator and the SLA, respectively, remain within low price ranges. The *input* function costs between \$0.021 and \$0.035, while the *output* function costs remains between \$0.048 and \$0.166.

On the other hand, running the game on-chain entails much higher costs, ranging from \$0.287 (with $SP = 2$) to \$7.273 (with $SP = 8$). In addition, it is important to note that the maximum values can reach up to \$117 in the case of 8 SPs. These high values are due to factors such as the increased memory requirements and the higher number of iterations needed to converge to an equilibrium point in the game’s resolution process, as analysed in Section IV.

2) IMPACT OF THE NUMBER OF NOs

As concluded in Section VIII-A, fixing the number of SPs to $S=4$, any change in the number of NOs only impacts the execution cost of the *output* and *solveStackelberg* functions. As can be observed in Table 2b, the average cost of executing the *output*, when considering 10 NOs, is approximately \$0.20, with observed values ranging from a minimum of \$0.038 to a maximum of \$3.302. This cost exhibits a notable increase when the game execution occurs on-chain. In such cases, the average cost can reach approximately \$3.63, with occasional spikes up to nearly \$59. The variation in these values is primarily driven by factors such as network congestion, gas prices, and the complexity of the transactions involved, as previously explained.

C. IMPACT OF USING AN ORACLE FOR AUTOMATING THE GAME EXECUTION

In this section, we evaluate the suitability of automating and delegating the execution of the SLA operation to invoke the MLMF functions. As explained in Section VI-B, this approach would avoid assigning these functions to one of the game participants. To perform this analysis, we select two well-known decentralized oracles, Chainlink [69] and Gelato [70], which allow execution of SC functions when

FIGURE 12. Estimated average cost of the *initialize*, *setBandwidth*, *startInput* and *endInput* functions (measured in USD) over 12-month period (November 2023 to October 2024).

TABLE 1. Estimated cost of the proposed solution (in U.S. dollars) for $C = 4$ CF-mMIMO networks and $S = 4$ SPs and considering the average, minimum and maximum gas prices paid over a 12-month period and their standard deviation (Nov. 2023 to Oct. 2024).

	deploy SLA	<i>initialize</i>	<i>setBandwidth</i>	<i>startInput</i>	<i>input</i>	<i>endInput</i>	<i>output</i>	<i>solveStack</i> .	
Polygon	avg	0.554	0.005	0.011	0.003	0.026	0.003	0.087	1.338
	min	0.102	0.001	0.002	0.001	0.005	0.001	0.016	0.246
	max	8.952	0.079	0.18	0.049	0.417	0.049	1.413	21.604
	std	0.674	0.006	0.014	0.004	0.031	0.004	0.106	1.626
BNB	avg	10.905	0.096	0.22	0.06	0.508	0.06	1.721	26.317
	min	4.091	0.036	0.082	0.023	0.191	0.023	0.645	9.872
	max	58.471	0.514	1.179	0.322	2.723	0.323	9.226	141.113
	std	4.693	0.041	0.095	0.026	0.219	0.026	0.74	11.325
Arbitrum	avg	0.907	0.008	0.018	0.005	0.042	0.005	0.143	2.19
	min	0.121	0.001	0.002	0.001	0.006	0.001	0.019	0.292
	max	39.809	0.35	0.802	0.22	1.854	0.22	6.282	96.074
	std	2.301	0.02	0.046	0.013	0.107	0.013	0.363	5.553
Fantom	avg	0.4	0.004	0.008	0.002	0.019	0.002	0.063	0.965
	min	0.037	$< 10^{-3}$	0.001	$< 10^{-3}$	0.002	$< 10^{-3}$	0.006	0.09
	max	8.53	0.075	0.172	0.047	0.397	0.047	1.346	20.587
	std	0.784	0.007	0.016	0.004	0.037	0.004	0.124	1.892

predefined conditions are met, as well as execution of off-chain operations and publishing the results to an specified SC.

As evaluated in Section VIII-B, the execution of on-chain functions comes with an economic cost that is paid by the entity that executes them. Therefore, in the proposed system, the oracle could assume this cost when executing the MLMF functions. The entity that delegates the execution of a function compensates the oracle for this economic cost and

provides an additional fee to reward the oracle for participating in the system. In the two evaluated oracles, this additional fee is a percentage of the economic cost of executing the function, usually called the premium [71], [72]. The premium can vary between blockchains, for example in Chainlink and Gelato the premium is set to 70% in Polygon, but in Ethereum it is set to 20%.

In addition to the premium fee, there is another factor to consider in Chainlink's billing. Chainlink allows multiple

TABLE 2. Estimated cost of the proposed solution (in U.S. dollars) and considering the average, minimum and maximum gas prices paid over a 12-month period and their standard deviation (Nov. 2023 to Oct. 2024).

(a) For $C = 4$ CF-mMIMO networks										(b) For $S = 4$ SPs						
S	input			output			solveStack.			C	output			solveStack.		
	2	4	8	2	4	8	2	4	8		2	5	10	2	5	10
avg	0.021	0.026	0.035	0.048	0.087	0.166	0.287	1.338	7.273	avg	0.048	0.107	0.204	0.652	1.771	3.632
min	0.004	0.005	0.007	0.009	0.016	0.03	0.053	0.246	1.339	min	0.009	0.02	0.038	0.12	0.326	0.669
max	0.339	0.417	0.573	0.782	1.413	2.673	4.641	21.604	117.446	max	0.782	1.728	3.302	10.528	28.597	58.653
std	0.025	0.031	0.043	0.059	0.106	0.201	0.349	1.626	8.838	std	0.059	0.13	0.249	0.792	2.152	4.414

(a) For $C = 4$ CF-mMIMO networks

(b) For $S = 4$ SPs

delegated functions to be executed in a single transaction. This means that Chainlink’s SCs carry out more operations, which leads to extra costs. To cover these additional costs, they are shared among the entities that have delegated their functions to Chainlink.

In summary, considering g_p is the transaction gas price, g_u is the amount of gas used to execute the delegated function, g_o is the extra amount of gas used by Chainlink¹¹ (cost 0 for Gelato) and p is the premium percentage in the oracle, the transaction cost $txCost$ for executing a function is:

$$txCost = g_p(g_u + g_o)(1 + p) \quad (25a)$$

Since the economic cost without oracles can be expressed as the transaction gas price (g_p) multiplied by the gas used (g_u), the overhead (or the extra) cost of executing a single function compared to executing it directly without any oracle ($\Delta txCost$) is given by:

$$\Delta txCost = g_p g_u p + g_p g_o (1 + p) \quad (26a)$$

Chainlink and Gelato provide a service to delegate the execution of operations to the nodes of the oracle network instead of encoding them in a SC. In the off-chain version of the proposed solution, this service can be used to compute the Stackelberg game off-chain and publish the results to the MLMF SC. However, this service typically comes with limitations on computational resources. For example, Chainlink limits the maximum data return size to 128 bytes, which restricts the Stackelberg game execution to $C = 1$ and $S = 2$ or $C = 2$ and $S = 1$. Gelato, on the other hand, does not have this limitation, but has additional restrictions on the number of executions allowed that can be overcome, if required, at an additional cost.

The overhead cost of executing the MLMF functions through Chainlink and Gelato (modeled by equation (26a)) has been analyzed considering the average estimated cost of each function in Polygon presented in Table 1. As expected, the use of Chainlink results in higher overhead costs than Gelato. If the resolution of the Stackelberg game resolution is handled off-chain, the total overhead cost is 0.108 for Chainlink and 0.068 for Gelato. If the resolution occurs on-chain, the overhead increases to 1.003 for Chainlink and 0.943 for Gelato.

¹¹It is assumed that there are 80,000 units of extra gas, as it is reflected in the documentation [71].

Therefore, the additional cost of automating the SLA functions with an oracle may not appear significant and would help avoid assigning game management responsibilities to specific participants. However, it is important to examine how this cost might impact the long-term execution of the game.

1) BALANCE BETWEEN COST AND LATENCY

The financial feasibility of the proposed solution has been evaluated by considering the average cost of executing the MLMF on the blockchain. However, another critical factor influencing the total cost is the latency introduced by blockchain usage. Generally, for a given blockchain, the shorter the execution time required for a function, the higher the fee to be paid [73]. Next, we perform the evaluation, defining a game round as the execution of the main MLMF functions in a scenario with $C = 4$ and $S = 4$. We assume that all *setBandwidth* functions are published in the same blockchain block, as well as all *input* functions. From now on, we will refer to the *initialize*, *startInput*, *endInput* and *output* functions as administrative tasks of a game round, as they all need to be executed by the SLA.

For the analysis, we use the gas price to reach the minimum delay¹² published in PolygonScan [74], BNBScan [75] and FTMScan [76], to get the results for Polygon, BNB Smart Chain and Fantom, respectively.¹³ The minimum delay found is between 5 and 10 seconds for all these sources. While this represents the minimum reported latency, it should not be interpreted as the lowest achievable delay, as it is influenced by the gas price paid, as previously discussed. Tab. 3 summarizes the analysis results.

Polygon and Fantom stand out as the blockchains with the lowest transaction costs (as shown in Section VIII-B), especially considering that all analysed blockchains have almost identical publication times. The cost of performing MLMF functions on Fantom is about 50% lower than on Polygon. For example, an operator would pay approximately \$0.01 to publish parameters on Fantom, while the cost on Polygon would be approximately \$0.018. SPs incur about half the cost of NOs (\$0.004 on Fantom and \$0.008 on

¹²We have not found a source to get the estimated transaction delays given the gas price for the blockchains analysed in this work.

¹³We have not found a source to get the gas price to reach the minimum delay for the Arbitrum network.

TABLE 3. Trade-off between delay and price for $C = 4$ CF-mMIMO networks and $S = 4$ SPs; average price for a minimum delay in Polygon, BNB Smart Chain and Fantom.

Blockchain		Polygon	BNB	Fantom
delay (s)		5-10	5-10	5-10
admin	output	0.068	0.714	0.039
	(overhead)	0.088	0.537	0.04
	solveStack.	0.932	9.782	0.538
	(overhead)	0.693	3.258	0.29
SP	setBandwidth	0.008	0.081	0.004
NO	input	0.018	0.187	0.01

Polygon). The highest administrative costs, particularly when interacting with the Oracle, are around \$0.156 on Polygon and \$0.079 on Fantom. While these individual costs may seem negligible, recall that the Stackelberg game can be run periodically, leading to significant cumulative costs over time.

2) COST OF RUNNING STACKELBERG ON A REGULAR BASIS

In certain scenarios, the Stackelberg game may need to be executed periodically, making it crucial to analyze both the overall management cost of the game and the specific costs incurred by each SP and NO.

Table 4 summarizes the daily and monthly cost of executing a game round in the two cheapest blockchains (Polygon and Fantom), in a cadence of 10 seconds, 10 minutes or one hour for each participant: the manager (who executes the administration tasks), SPs and NOs. Each SP pays the cost of executing the *setBandwidth* function to publish its available bandwidth. Meanwhile, each NO pays the cost of executing the *input* function to publish its network parameters.

As observed, the cost of using the blockchain decreases significantly as the frequency of game execution decreases, which is an expected result. For example, when using Polygon and considering the daily cost, one NO's cost would drop from around \$154.14 (when participating in the game every 10 seconds) to just \$0.43 when participating once per hour. Similarly, for a SP, the cost would drop from about \$66.71 to just \$0.19. In the case of Fantom, these costs are reduced by more than half compared to Polygon, as was seen in Section VIII-C.1. For example, an operator would pay about \$38.51 versus \$66.71 if the game run every 10 seconds.

Using an oracle for frequent administrative tasks, such as executing the Stackelberg game every 10 minutes, significantly increases operational costs. In this case, the monthly cost can reach around \$673 on Polygon, with about \$380 attributed to the oracle overhead. It should be noted that the cost of administration can be distributed among the number of participants in the system. As previously noted, this analysis has assumed $C = 4$ and $S = 4$, which would imply eight participants contributing to system maintenance costs. Assuming equal contributions from all participants,

the cost per participant of publishing game results with an oracle would be approximately \$84 in Polygon and less than \$43 in Fantom.

D. BLOCKCHAIN PERFORMANCE MEASURED IN TRANSACTIONS PER SECOND

In this section, we conduct an analysis of the blockchain performance and scalability, beyond the economic costs and transaction delays associated with blockchain publication. This evaluation considers the number of transactions per second (TPS) that different public blockchains can handle (see Table 5).

The maximum theoretical throughput of a blockchain is calculated by dividing the number of transactions that can fit into a block by the duration of the block. The capacity of the block, measured in gas units, determines the maximum number of transactions it can hold. As shown in the Table 5, most blockchains allow up to 30 million gas units per block, except for BNB, which supports up to 140 million gas units.

Each blockchain has a predefined block time. For example, Arbitrum has the shortest block time at 250 milliseconds, while Ethereum has the longest at 12 seconds. These factors determine the maximum possible throughput of the network. For example, with a block duration of 250 milliseconds and a block gas limit of 32 million, Arbitrum could theoretically process 1,428 transactions per block, resulting in a maximum theoretical throughput of 6,095 TPS. In contrast, Ethereum currently supports around 119 TPS, although Ethereum 2.0 aims to reach 100,000 TPS in the future.

However, these values are theoretical, and actual performance will vary due to fluctuations in block sizes, network congestion, and other operational factors. Looking at the highest recorded TPS, Solana has the highest value with 2,909 TPS, followed by BNB (1,731 TPS) and Arbitrum (1,105 TPS).

Real-time throughput over a 30-day period (see Table 5), shows that Solana achieves 679 TPS, Polygon around 40 TPS, and Ethereum only 15 TPS. It is important to highlight that blockchain performance continues to improve over time. For instance, Ethereum aims to reach 100,000 TPS in the future. Meanwhile, Solana has been designed as a high-performance, scalable, and fast blockchain, featuring a block time of just 400 milliseconds, minimal transaction costs, and a theoretical throughput of up to 65,000 TPS. These results indicate that blockchains can support significantly higher loads than those currently utilized, highlighting their potential for future scalability.

Remarkably, our proposed system allows the execution of multiple Stackelberg game rounds in parallel, while also enabling the deployment of various MLMF smart contracts to accommodate different system conditions (as explained in Section VI-A). These smart contracts could even be deployed on different blockchains to adapt to changing time and cost requirements over time. This adaptability and versatility of the proposed solution allow it to adjust to different scenarios, ensuring optimal performance and cost efficiency.

TABLE 4. Estimated cost summary for executing a complete Stackelberg game round per day and per month, considering various frequencies and utilizing Polygon and Fantom.

Blockchain			Polygon			Fantom			
Cadence			10s	10min	1h	10s	10min	1h	
daily cost	admin	output	no-oracle	587.896	9.798	1.633	339.429	5.657	0.943
			overhead	759.113	12.652	2.109	346.788	5.78	0.963
	solveStack.		no-oracle	8052.826	134.214	22.369	4649.399	77.49	12.915
			overhead	5984.563	99.743	16.624	2501.773	41.696	6.949
	SP			66.708	1.112	0.185	38.515	0.642	0.107
	NO			154.137	2.569	0.428	88.993	1.483	0.247
monthly cost	admin	output	no-oracle	17636.894	293.948	48.991	10182.88	169.715	28.286
			overhead	22773.386	379.556	63.259	10403.629	173.394	28.899
	solveStack.		no-oracle	241584.779	4026.413	671.069	139481.974	2324.7	387.45
			overhead	179536.905	2992.282	498.714	75053.176	1250.886	208.481
	SP			2001.248	33.354	5.559	1155.445	19.257	3.21
	NO			4624.124	77.069	12.845	2669.796	44.497	7.416

TABLE 5. Summary of the analysis of different public blockchains: blockchain parameters and blockchain performance (Data source: Chainspect, blockchain analytics platform <https://chainspect.app/dashboard>, data accessed on March 28, 2025)).

	Ethereum	BNB	Fantom	Avalanche	Solana	Polygon	Optimism	Arbitrum
Blockchain type	Layer-1	Layer-1	Layer-1	Layer-1	Layer-1	Layer-2	Layer-2	Layer-2
Block gas limit (millions)	30	140	31	15	-	30	30	32
Block time (seconds)	12.1	3	1.38	1.74	0.4	2.18	2	0.25
Real-Time throughput (30-day period) (TPS)	14.73	57.64	3.07	4.18	679	39.16	11.15	21.74
Max recorded throughput (TPS)	62.34	1,731	181	123	2,909	429	91.74	1,105
Max theoretical throughput (TPS)	119	2,222	1,476	1,191	65,000	714	714	6,095

IX. CONCLUSION

This work presents a generalized framework for automated, transparent, and fair DSS within 6G networks. Specifically, multiple NOs using the CF-mMIMO topology are considered buyers of bandwidth from multiple SPs. The spectrum trade is modeled as a Stackelberg game, where SPs maximize the price per bandwidth unit, while NOs optimize a utility function balancing SE gains and bandwidth costs. An iterative algorithm is proposed to solve the game, guaranteeing convergence to a unique equilibrium.

The game’s organization and resolution require information exchange between SPs and NOs. Blockchain ensures transparency and traceability by recording all actions for auditability. It also enables automated decisions, reducing intermediaries and improving spectrum allocation. The defined SC structure offers adaptability to changes in parameters, participants, or execution rules.

Extensive simulations show how network configurations (e.g., number of NOs and SPs) influence game outcomes and pricing. The game-solving protocol is implemented on several blockchain platforms to assess the real costs of the proposed DSS framework. Notably, the blockchain choice significantly affects cost efficiency. Offloading game

execution to an oracle was also tested on two commercial platforms, incurring minimal overhead, highlighting the trade-off between reduced computational burden and added costs.

On the cell-free side, future work will study the impact of hardware impairments on game outcomes and how mismatched information affects blockchain data requirements. On the blockchain side, the next step involves evaluating the cost and performance of deploying on permissioned blockchains. This includes analyzing network settings such as consensus algorithms, block sizes, and participant roles. The economic costs of running and maintaining nodes will also be assessed, as these factors are critical to security, participant trust, and overall operational expenses.

**APPENDIX A
PROOF OF LEMMA 1**

Setting the first derivative of $U_c(\mathbf{b}_c^{(CF)}, \mathbf{p}_c^{(CF)})$ in (12) equal to zero, it is straightforwardly shown that

$$b_{cs} = \frac{\eta_c \alpha_{cs}}{\beta_{cs} - \gamma_c} - \frac{p_{cs}}{\beta_{cs} - \gamma_c} - \frac{\gamma_c}{\beta_{cs} - \gamma_c} \sum_{s'=1}^S b_{cs'}, \quad (27)$$

for all $s \in \mathcal{S}$. Adding all the chunks of bandwidth in $\mathbf{b}_c^{(CF)}$ it follows that

$$\sum_{s=1}^S b_{cs} = \frac{\eta_c \sum_{s=1}^S \frac{\alpha_{cs}}{\beta_{cs} - \gamma_c} - \sum_{s=1}^S \frac{p_{cs}}{\beta_{cs} - \gamma_c}}{1 + \gamma_c \sum_{s=1}^S \frac{1}{\beta_{cs} - \gamma_c}}. \quad (28)$$

Substituting (28) into (27) and operating leads to

$$b_{cs} = \zeta_{cs} - \varpi_{cs} p_{cs} + \kappa_{cs} \left(\mathbf{p}_{c-s}^{(CF)} \right), \quad (29)$$

with ζ_{cs} , ϖ_{cs} and $\kappa_{cs}(\mathbf{p}_{c-s}^{(CF)})$ defined in (15). Finally, the projection of b_{cs} onto the set of non-negative real numbers provides (14).

APPENDIX B PROOF OF LEMMA 2

The Lagrangian of the convex optimization problem **PSPR** can be expressed as

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{L}(\mathbf{p}_s^{(SP)}, \lambda_s, \mathbf{v}_s, \xi_s) &= \sum_{c=1}^C p_{cs} \left(\zeta_{cs} - \varpi_{cs} p_{cs} + \kappa_{cs} \left(\mathbf{p}_{c-s}^{(CF)} \right) \right) \\ &+ \lambda_s \left(B_s - \sum_{c=1}^C \left(\zeta_{cs} - \varpi_{cs} p_{cs} + \kappa_{cs} \left(\mathbf{p}_{c-s}^{(CF)} \right) \right) \right) \\ &+ \sum_{c=1}^C v_{cs} p_{cs} - \sum_{c=1}^C \xi_{cs} \left(p_{cs} - \frac{\zeta_{cs} + \kappa_{cs} \left(\mathbf{p}_{c-s}^{(CF)} \right)}{\varpi_{cs}} \right). \end{aligned} \quad (30)$$

where λ_{cs} , v_{cs} and ξ_{cs} are the Lagrange multipliers. The KKT conditions for this problem are given as follows: *Stationarity*:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}(\mathbf{p}_s^{(SP)}, \lambda_s, \mathbf{v}_s, \xi_s)}{\partial p_{cs}} &= \zeta_{cs} + \kappa_{cs} \left(\mathbf{p}_{c-s}^{(CF)} \right) \\ -2\varpi_{cs} p_{cs} + \lambda_s \varpi_{cs} + v_{cs} - \xi_{cs} &= 0, \end{aligned} \quad (31a)$$

Complementary slackness:

$$\lambda_s \left(B_s - \sum_{c=1}^C \left(\zeta_{cs} - \varpi_{cs} p_{cs} + \kappa_{cs} \left(\mathbf{p}_{c-s}^{(CF)} \right) \right) \right) = 0, \quad (31b)$$

$$v_{cs} p_{cs} = 0 \quad \forall c \in \mathcal{C}, \quad (31c)$$

$$\xi_{cs} \left(p_{cs} - \frac{\zeta_{cs} + \kappa_{cs} \left(\mathbf{p}_{c-s}^{(CF)} \right)}{\varpi_{cs}} \right) = 0 \quad \forall c \in \mathcal{C}, \quad (31d)$$

Primal feasibility:

$$\sum_{c=1}^C \left(\zeta_{cs} - \varpi_{cs} p_{cs} + \kappa_{cs} \left(\mathbf{p}_{c-s}^{(CF)} \right) \right) \leq B_s, \quad (31e)$$

$$p_{cs} \geq 0 \quad \forall c \in \mathcal{C}, \quad (31f)$$

$$p_{cs} \leq \left(\zeta_{cs} + \kappa_{cs} \left(\mathbf{p}_{c-s}^{(CF)} \right) \right) / \varpi_{cs} \quad \forall c \in \mathcal{C}, \quad (31g)$$

Dual feasibility:

$$\lambda_s \geq 0, \quad (31h)$$

$$v_{cs} \geq 0 \quad \forall c \in \mathcal{C}, \quad (31i)$$

$$\xi_{cs} \geq 0 \quad \forall c \in \mathcal{C}. \quad (31j)$$

Lemma 4: The prices per unit of bandwidth are always positive, that is, $p_{cs} > 0$ for all $c \in \mathcal{C}$. Moreover, the Lagrange multipliers $v_{cs} = 0$ for all $c \in \mathcal{C}$.

Proof: Let us assume that $p_{cs} = 0$ for an arbitrary CF-mMIMO network c . In this case, from (31d) it follows that $\xi_{cs} = 0$. Thus, using $p_{cs} = 0$ and $\xi_{cs} = 0$ in (31a) yields

$$\zeta_{cs} + \kappa_{cs} \left(\mathbf{p}_{c-s}^{(CF)} \right) + \lambda_s \varpi_{cs} + v_{cs} = 0. \quad (32)$$

As stated in Lemma 1, the parameters ζ_{cs} , ϖ_{cs} , and $\kappa_{cs}(\mathbf{p}_{c-s}^{(CF)})$ are positive. Furthermore, from (31h) and (31i) it is known that $\lambda_s \geq 0$ and $v_{cs} \geq 0$, respectively. Under these conditions, equation (32) is incompatible. The conclusion is then that $p_{cs} > 0$ for all $c \in \mathcal{C}$ and from (31c) it follows that $v_{cs} = 0$ for all $c \in \mathcal{C}$. ■

Lemma 5: The primal feasibility constraint (31e) is satisfied with equality, that is,

$$\sum_{c=1}^C \left(\zeta_{cs} - \varpi_{cs} p_{cs} + \kappa_{cs} \left(\mathbf{p}_{c-s}^{(CF)} \right) \right) = B_s, \quad (33)$$

and the Lagrange multiplier $\lambda_s \neq 0$.

Proof: Let us assume that $\lambda_s = 0$ and let us select a particular CF-mMIMO NO c for which the primal feasibility constraint (31g) is inactive, that is, a CF-mMIMO NO for which $p_{cs} < (\zeta_{cs} + \kappa_{cs}(\mathbf{p}_{c-s}^{(CF)})) / \varpi_{cs}$. Using the complementary slackness condition (31d), it follows that $\xi_{cs} = 0$. Hence, using Lemma 4 (i.e., $v_{cs} = 0$), and the assumptions that $\lambda_s = 0$ and $\xi_{cs} = 0$ in the stationarity condition (31a) entails that the only possible solution would be

$$p_{cs} = \frac{\zeta_{cs} + \kappa_{cs} \left(\mathbf{p}_{c-s}^{(CF)} \right)}{2\varpi_{cs}}, \quad (34)$$

which is incompatible with the fact that, in general, p_{cs} could potentially take any value in the range $0 < p_{cs} < (\zeta_{cs} + \kappa_{cs}(\mathbf{p}_{c-s}^{(CF)})) / \varpi_{cs}$. The conclusion is then that $\lambda_s \neq 0$ and from the complementary slackness constraint (31b) it holds that the primal feasibility constraint (31e) is active. ■

Let us define the sets \mathcal{C}_{A_s} and \mathcal{C}_{I_s} as the sets of NOs for which the dual feasibility constraint (31j) is either active or inactive, respectively. That is,

$$\mathcal{C}_{A_s} = \{c : \xi_{cs} > 0\}, \quad (35a)$$

$$\mathcal{C}_{I_s} = \{c : \xi_{cs} = 0\}. \quad (35b)$$

Using these definitions and applying Lemma 4 in the stationarity condition (31a), it follows that

$$p_{cs} = \begin{cases} \frac{\zeta_{cs} + \kappa_{cs} \left(\mathbf{p}_{c-s}^{(CF)} \right)}{\varpi_{cs}} & \forall c \in \mathcal{C}_{A_s} \\ \frac{\zeta_{cs} + \kappa_{cs} \left(\mathbf{p}_{c-s}^{(CF)} \right)}{2\varpi_{cs}} + \frac{\lambda_s}{2} & \forall c \in \mathcal{C}_{I_s}. \end{cases} \quad (36)$$

Now, using these prices jointly with the equality condition deduced in Lemma 5 it can be established that

$$\lambda_s = \frac{\sum_{c \in \mathcal{C}_{I_s}} \left(\zeta_{cs} + \kappa_{cs} \left(\mathbf{p}_{c-s}^{(CF)} \right) \right) - 2B_s}{\sum_{c \in \mathcal{C}_{I_s}} \varpi_{cs}}. \quad (37)$$

Using again Lemma 4 in the stationarity condition (31a) leads to the conclusion that

$$\xi_{cs} = \lambda_s \varpi_{cs} - \zeta_{cs} - \kappa_{cs}(\mathbf{p}_{c-s}^{(CF)}) \quad \forall c \in \mathcal{C}_{A_s}, \quad (38)$$

which must be positive and, therefore, it can be inferred that

$$\frac{\zeta_{cs} + \kappa_{cs}(\mathbf{p}_{c-s}^{(CF)})}{\varpi_{cs}} < \lambda_s \quad \forall c \in \mathcal{C}_{A_s}, \quad (39)$$

and results presented in Lemma 2 can be straightforwardly deduced.

APPENDIX C PROOF OF LEMMA 3

Definition 1: A function $F(\mathbf{p})$ is said to be standard and satisfies the two-sided scalability property if the following conditions hold for all $\mathbf{p} \succeq \mathbf{0}$:

- 1) *Positivity:* $F(\mathbf{p}) > 0$
- 2) *Monotonicity:* For all \mathbf{p} and \mathbf{p}' , if $\mathbf{p} \succ \mathbf{p}'$, then $F(\mathbf{p}) > F(\mathbf{p}')$.
- 3) *Scalability:* For all $\mu > 1$, $\mu F(\mathbf{p}) > F(\mu \mathbf{p})$.
- 4) *Two-sided scalability:* For all $\mu > 1$, if $\frac{1}{\mu} \mathbf{p} \preceq \mathbf{p}' \preceq \mu \mathbf{p}$, then $\frac{1}{\mu} F(\mathbf{p}) < F(\mathbf{p}') < \mu F(\mathbf{p})$.

Lemma 6: The function

$$F(\mathbf{p}_{c-s}^{(CF)}) = \begin{cases} \frac{\zeta_{cs} + \kappa_{cs}(\mathbf{p}_{c-s}^{(CF)})}{2\varpi_{cs}} + \frac{\lambda_s}{2} & \forall c \in \{c_{s1}, \dots, c_{s(\tau_s-1)}\} \\ \frac{\zeta_{cs} + \kappa_{cs}(\mathbf{p}_{c-s}^{(CF)})}{\varpi_{cs}} & \forall c \in \{c_{s\tau_s}, \dots, c_{sC}\}, \end{cases} \quad (40)$$

is a standard function and satisfies the two-sided scalability property.

Proof:

Positivity: As stated in Lemma 1, the parameters of the system must be set in order to guarantee that ζ_{cs} , ϖ_{cs} , and $\kappa_{cs}(\mathbf{p}_{c-s}^{(CF)})$ are all positive. Moreover, from Lemma 5 and the dual feasibility constraint (31h), we know that $\lambda_s > 0$. Then, it follows that $F(\mathbf{p}_{c-s}^{(CF)}) > 0$.

Monotonicity: For all $\mathbf{p}_{c-s}^{(CF)} \succ \mathbf{p}'_{c-s}^{(CF)}$, it holds that $\kappa_{cs}(\mathbf{p}_{c-s}^{(CF)}) > \kappa_{cs}(\mathbf{p}'_{c-s}^{(CF)})$ and, consequently, $F(\mathbf{p}_{c-s}^{(CF)}) > F(\mathbf{p}'_{c-s}^{(CF)})$.

Scalability: For all $\mu > 1$, we have that $\kappa_{cs}(\mu \mathbf{p}_{c-s}^{(CF)}) = \mu \kappa_{cs}(\mathbf{p}'_{c-s}^{(CF)})$ and hence, as $\zeta_{cs} > 0$, and $\varpi_{cs} > 0$ it follows that $\mu F(\mathbf{p}_{c-s}^{(CF)}) > F(\mu \mathbf{p}_{c-s}^{(CF)})$.

Two-sided scalability: For all $\mu > 1$, we have that whenever $\frac{1}{\mu} \mathbf{p}_{c-s}^{(CF)} \preceq \mathbf{p}'_{c-s}^{(CF)} \preceq \mu \mathbf{p}_{c-s}^{(CF)}$ then $\frac{1}{\mu} \kappa_{cs}(\mathbf{p}_{c-s}^{(CF)}) \leq \kappa_{cs}(\mathbf{p}'_{c-s}^{(CF)}) \leq \mu \kappa_{cs}(\mathbf{p}_{c-s}^{(CF)})$ and consequently, $\frac{1}{\mu} F(\mathbf{p}_{c-s}^{(CF)}) \leq F(\mathbf{p}'_{c-s}^{(CF)}) \leq \mu F(\mathbf{p}_{c-s}^{(CF)})$. ■

According to [77], [78], [79], an iterative update of a standard function satisfying the two-sided scalability property converges to the corresponding fixed point and consequently, this completes the proof.

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